

ANIMA

Aviation Noise Impact Management
through Novel Approaches

D3.4 -PILOT STUDY ON NOVEL LAND-USE PLANNING (LUP) APPROACHES:

**HOW A SOUNDSCAPE MOBILE APP
CAN INFORM LUP DECISIONS AND
OPERATIONAL PROCEDURES**

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DEM=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
DEC=Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.
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1. Executive Summary

Aircraft noise is one of the most significant local environmental impacts related to aviation operations. While individual aircraft may have become quieter due to airframe and engine technology advances, an increase in the number of flights and urbanisation, with cities spreading outwards and nearer to airports, have led to more people being affected by aviation noise. More information on the locations, and times that people are exposed to aircraft noise, can lead to a better understanding of their reactions and complaints, smarter land-use planning and more effective operational procedures around airports to mitigate the negative impacts of aircraft noise.

This study sought to contribute to a greater understanding of people’s perception of soundscape in general and, thereby, infer the effects of noise on the quality of life of residents near airports. Recent technological advances have enabled an increased opportunity to conduct novel sound research by deploying novel, tailored mobile phone applications. In this case, **the AnimApp was developed and used to collect a range of momentary situational and environmental perception data to determine whether such information can help to improve understanding of the effects of noise on humans.** The specific intention was to carry out an experience sampling method (ESM) study about the impact of the soundscape and visual environment on people’s perception of their environment and quality of life around airports. However, the project’s timing meant that the app was deployed during the period of COVID pandemic restrictions in the early summer of 2021. Thus, the aim had to be adapted to reflect that a) air traffic volumes were significantly reduced and b) that people’s activities were affected by mobility and accessibility restrictions.

Thus, in this study, efforts were made to:

- collect all the information necessary to better describe the way people interact with their sound environment,
- study the influence of the sound environment on wellbeing and quality of life, and
- understand the role of the air traffic noise in the composition of the sound environment around airports, not only acoustically, but essentially perceptively (since aircraft sound is only one aspect of the environment).

The methods underpinning the development of the AnimApp were divided into pre-release and release phases.

The pre-release phase 1 consisted of

- (i) the elaboration of the test-method (i.e. what should participants be asked),
- (ii) the development of the app on both iPhone and Android platforms,

-
- (iii) initial testing of the app to generate feedback on the content and useability of the app.

The release phase 2 consisted of

- (i) refinement of the test-method in the light of the feedback from test participants,
(ii) modification of the app and release in the App- and Play-stores,
(iii) recruitment aiming for 60 participants around two airports (i.e. London-Heathrow and Ljubljana airports – later opened up to include other UK airports to increase number of responses),
(iv) conducting the field study,
(v) evaluation of the gathered data.

As anticipated, due to the timing of the deployment in unusual circumstances, the number of people participating was low. Only a relatively small number of participants (47) fulfilled all the minimum requirements for inclusion in the data analysis.

Nevertheless, **the survey provided good information on functionality of the mobile application. It also revealed that a lot of diverse and important information can be gathered in a relatively easy and novel way.** On the other hand, considering the specific circumstances and the small data sample, **it is important that results of the data analysis are seen as illustrative of how the AnimApp data may be analysed.** The main findings are:

- In comparison to traditional methods of exploring the sound environment around airports such as noise contours, this application enables more nuanced capture of the lived experience of the soundscape.
- The application enables exploration of the relationship between momentary soundscape and quality of life – something that can augment stakeholder understanding of the impacts of aircraft noise on communities.
- The application collects both acoustic and perceptual data allowing assessment of potentially rich interactions between subjective and objective metrics with a very common device, the user's mobile phone.
- Methods that capture the dynamism of daily life can yield improved insights into the experience of sound in different locations and at different times.
- The pilot study was a successful proof of the AnimApp concept which gives a clear indication that sound level alone is not enough to assess impact of sound on peoples' wellbeing and quality of life.

- The AnimApp can be easily used and can give an opportunity to land use planners, decision makers and citizens to better understand and judge the environment where they live.
- The AnimApp can help inform better decisions for providing supportive and healthy living conditions near airports.

2. Introduction

2.1. Background and aim of the subtask

Aircraft noise is one of the most significant local environmental impacts related to aviation operations. With urban migration and growth, the spatial change in cities and conurbations means that urban areas are now closer to airports. Air traffic volumes have also grown and, although individual aircraft may actually have become quieter due to advances in airframe and engine technology, the rising number of flights has led to an increase in the number of people affected by aviation noise. A more thorough understanding of the locations, and times that people are exposed to aircraft noise, can lead to smarter land-use planning and operational procedures around airports in order to mitigate the negative impacts of aircraft noise.

Recent technological advances have driven developments in knowledge in the field of noise research. There has also been an associated increase in opportunities to conduct novel research. This deliverable discusses the use of a mobile phone-based application to assess the perception of soundscape (positive/negative) in general and, thereby, infer the effects of noise on the quality of life of people living in the proximity of airports.

This report presents the findings of a sub-task (3.3.2) of ANIMA Work Package 3. The initial objective of the sub-task was to determine whether the data obtained via a novel technological application helped to improve understanding of the effects of noise on humans. The specific intention was to carry out an experience sampling method (ESM) study about the impact of the soundscape and visual environment on people's perception of their environment and quality of life around airports. However, the project's timing meant that the app was deployed during the period of COVID pandemic restrictions. Thus, the aim had to be adapted to reflect that a) air traffic volumes were significantly reduced and b) that people's activities were affected by mobility and accessibility restrictions. Therefore, **the aim evolved into trialling the usability of the app for the purpose of capturing instantaneous perceptions of participants experience of their soundscape including aircraft noise when present.**

In the following Section 3, an overview of the context in which the application was developed is provided. Section 4 describes the actual application development. The analysis of data from the app study and examination of findings is in Section 5. This is followed, in Section 6, by a discussion of key recommendations and conclusions.

3. Background information

3.1. Background on soundscape research

Given that the goal of this sub-task was to propose a participative method to understand the impact of sound environment on people who live around airports, a “soundscape” approach, where the sound environment is not only seen as a “waste” (as it could be with noise pollution), but also as a “resource” where life expresses itself with natural or human-made pleasant sounds, was adopted. In this study, an aircraft flyover was treated as one sound source, among others, and not as the only source of interest. This holistic approach started with Gibson (1986) and Gaver (1993) in the second part of the 20th century, who proposed focusing on the ecology of perception, seeking to understand how people interact with the physical world. In the same period, in Vancouver, the field of acoustic ecology took off in the pioneering works of Murray Schafer (1977) and the “World Soundscape Project”, making “soundscape” a key notion that is today widely used in acoustic research on the sound environment, both indoors and outdoors. More recently, in 2014, the definition of the “soundscape” was included in an International Standard: “The soundscape is the acoustic environment as perceived or experienced and/or understood by a person or people in a context” (ISO 12913-1, 2014). This definition, inspired by Barry Truax, (1978), puts the emphasis on the relationship between people and the environment. In the ISO standard, context takes into account interactions between people, activities, locations and moments. It also concerns psychological factors such as mood, or expectations. The acoustic environment is characterised by the sound sources which evolve in time and space. Therefore, in order to study the soundscape, it is important to collect such information which can influence people’s perceptions including their visual environment.

It follows, then, that with this soundscape approach, the way people perceive the sound environment is not treated as annoyance but as sound quality. Urban soundscape quality has been extensively studied (Viollon and Lavandier, 2000; Axelsson et al., 2010; Cain et al., 2013; Aletta et al., 2016; Jeon et al, 2018). A two-dimensional soundscape model of perceived quality emerged where one dimension corresponds to the “pleasantness” of the soundscape, and the orthogonal one corresponds to its “eventfulness” (Axelsson et al., 2010; Delaitre et al., 2014; Aumond et al., 2017). A third “familiarity” dimension is sometimes mentioned (Viollon and Lavandier, 2000; Axelsson et al., 2010).

Thus, in this study, efforts were made to:

- collect all the information necessary to better describe the way people interact with their sound environment,
- study the influence of the sound environment on wellbeing and quality of life,
- weight the load of the air traffic noise in the composition of the sound environment around airports, not only acoustically, but essentially

perceptively (since the aircraft sound is only one part of the acoustic environment).

3.2. Rationale for the app

The current methodology to quantify how many people are affected by aviation noise consists of developing noise contour maps of the yearly aircraft noise exposure and estimating the number of people affected by noise within these areas based on census data. When relying only on census information, inconsistencies might arise, since the residents may spend a considerable portion of the day outside the affected areas and, vice versa, people residing elsewhere may enter the affected areas to work or study, or for other reasons.

As opposed to the use of census data, the ANIMA project's approach incorporates the movements of the population during the day into the assessment of aircraft noise impact. In the case of the study described here, the mobile app is used to capture location and sound exposure via GPS.

The widespread use of small, powerful mobile devices enables a person-centric collection of environmental data, contributing to the opportunity to undertake participatory sensing (Burke et al, 2006; Kim et al, 2013). With integrated sensors (such as microphone and GPS) and the availability of broadband internet access, smartphones can now be used as low cost sound level monitoring tools. By 2010, smartphone sales had already surpassed those for personal computers, providing evidence that mobile devices were becoming fully integrated into everyday activities and supplanting existing computers as internet devices. Half of the world's population now has a mobile subscription and the increase has been substantial: from 3.6 billion in 2014 to 4.6 billion expected unique subscribers in 2020 (GSMA Mobile Economy, 2015). In this context, one particularly interesting application in environmental acoustics is to collect participatory sound measurements. Thus, several government and research organizations have already commissioned noise pollution monitoring studies using mobile phones (Maisonneuve et al, 2010; Rana et al, 2014; Bocher et al, 2015; Aspuru et al, 2016). As a result, there has been considerable progress in technologies for participatory mobile sound measurements, giving rise to the development of several applications such as SoundCity (Inria, 2015), EarPhone (Rana, 2010), NoiseSPY (Kanjo, 2010), and Noise-Tube (Maisonneuve, 2009). Many research efforts have then focused on the accuracy of the data gathered with these technologies inside and outside a laboratory (Kardous and Shaw, 2014; D'Hondt et al, 2013; Von Kaenel et al, 2011; Neitzel et al, 2016; Ibekwe et al, 2015).

3.3. The approach of experience sampling

A method for the assessment of event-related, acute or short-term self-reports is the Experience Sampling Method (ESM; Csikszentmihalyi & Larson 1992) or Ecological Momentary Assessment (EMA) method (Shiffman et al., 2008). ESM allows the repeated measurements of ongoing experiences of human-beings in-situ in different moments across a period of time (at different times of day, on several different days, etc.) in daily life. For this, respondents repeatedly fill in a

questionnaire in response to given signals/notifications. Recall bias that might occur in retrospective surveys is minimised when momentary experience, perception, mood, or behaviour is repeatedly assessed. As Bolger et al. (2003) put it, ESM like other diary methods allows "capturing life as it is lived" (p. 579).

In addition to other (paper-and-pencil) diaries, the ESM approach includes alerting respondents to report their acute or very recent short-term experience (e.g. within the last hour) (Bolger et al., 2003). The alert can be set by random or in fixed intervals. For today's ESM studies, mobile devices such as mobile phones are used.

Whereas for the assessment of noise annoyance in socio-acoustic field studies there is a long tradition of assessing annoyance as a long-term community response to noise (Bassarab et al., 2009) including efforts of internationally standardising the annoyance assessment (Fields et al., 2001; ISO/TS 15666), comparatively few studies exist that assess short-term annoyance in acute moments and/or close to the noise event. In noise effect research, ESM has been applied, for example, to assess short-term annoyance due to aircraft noise (Bartels et al., 2015; Page et al., 2020; Schreckenberg & Schuemer, 2010), due to road traffic and railway noise (Schreckenberg et al., 2004), and shooting noise (Großarth & Schreckenberg, 2019).

Compared to the situation in noise annoyance research, the assessment of the acute perception of the acoustic environment is well established in soundscape research. As the Figure of Aletta et al. (2016, Fig. 2, p. 71) shows (Figure 1), the soundscape research methodology comprises methods and tools for data collection of soundscape perception as experienced in situ, in simulations and reproductions of acoustic environment and as recalled from memory in retrospective surveys. For the assessment of acute (soundwalks) as well as recalled soundscape perception (surveys), an ISO/TS standard has been developed (ISO/TS 12913-2:2018).

Figure 1: Assessment methods for the perception of the acoustic environment in soundscape research. Source: Aletta et al. (2016, Fig. 2, p. 71)

The following examples show the use of ESM in soundscape research:

- Steffens et al. (2017) conducted a 7-day ESM study in Montreal, Canada, with 32 participants and 10 assessments per day per person with summary retrospective judgments at the end of the day and the week. The authors used a commercial Android ESM App (Movisens XS, Germany) for the assessments with the participant's smartphone. The participants were alerted randomly 10 times per day and within an individual 12-hours-time frame, which was defined by the participants at the beginning of the study. Furthermore, participants could start the app manually to additionally judge soundscapes that they experienced as exceptional, either positive or negative. With the app momentary judgments of the pleasantness, eventfulness and familiarity of the soundscape, the dominant sound source, the visual pleasantness of the environment and situational factors (location, attention paid to the soundscape, mood and activity) were assessed.
- In the study by Ricciardi et al. (2015), 60 participants each used a specific smartphone for sound recordings and judgments of sound perception in two districts of Paris for one year to assess 51 objectives in the winter period (September 2013 to February 2014) and again in the summer period (March to September 2014). With the electronic questionnaire various aspects of sound quality and sight preference were assessed and related to the recordings. A specific mobile phone application was developed for the data collection.
- In their ESM study, Fujiwara et al. (2017) studied the momentary social wellbeing (happiness) in airport regions in the UK several times per day. For the data collection, an iPhone app was used called 'Mappiness' that was developed specifically for the assessment of wellbeing. Along with the survey data, the GPS location and measurement time were also recorded. The GPS data and time of response were linked to modelled aircraft noise contour data and to the location of airport sites.

4. App development methodology

The methods underpinning the development of the AnimApp are described in this section following the chronology of the development process. This was divided into pre-release and release phases.

The pre-release phase one consisted of (i) the elaboration of the test-method (i.e. what should the participants be asked), (ii) the development of the app on both iPhone and Android platforms, (iii) initial testing of the app by a few participants directly recruited by the research team to generate feedback on the content and useability of the app. As during such studies it is of key importance that participants do not get overly annoyed by the test itself, so they stop somewhere in the middle, not only must the study procedure be well designed (scientifically as well as in terms of attractiveness), but the app itself must be as far as possible error-free and user-friendly. Related to former field studies, where paper-pencil or similar (i.e. very basic) computer programs have been used, the achievement of these two latter requirements formed a crucial part of the pre-release stage.

The release phase two consisted of (i) refinement of the test-method in the light of the feedback from test participants (ii) modification of the app and releasing it in the App- and Play-stores, (iii) recruitment aiming for 60 participants around two airports (i.e. London-Heathrow and Ljubljana airports) for the pilot study on the impact of the sound- and landscape of the surrounding environment on the people's perception of the environment and their quality of life, (iv) conducting the field study, (v) evaluation of the gathered data.

4.1. Phase One - Pre-release methodology

4.1.1. Phase One Stage(i) - Elaboration of the test methodology

Drawing upon previous ESM studies (outlined in 3.3 above), the research team identified a number of key areas on which data needed to be gathered in the momentary assessments and in reflective questionnaires to be completed at the end of a week of momentary samples, at the end of a weekend and at the completion of the survey. The specifications for the mobile application can be found in Annex 8.1 and the complete questionnaires in Annex 8.2.

The questions delivered during the momentary assessments (i.e. immediately after participants were notified and asked to complete a questionnaire) were intended to establish:

- Where and what activity the participant was engaged in at the time of the notification
- The nature of the visual environment (urban, rural, etc.)
- The participant's perception of the *general* environment in terms of its:
 - Pleasantness

- Eventfulness
- Familiarity
- The participant's perception of the *sound* environment in terms of its:
 - Pleasantness
 - Eventfulness
 - Impact on the activity being undertake

For each momentary assessment we also collected:

- The participant's general mood
- Measured acoustic data using the mobile device
- Calculated aircraft noise exposure within a one and a ten minute period of the notification to complete the momentary assessment (please see Annex 8.3 for further details)
- GPS location limited to 100x100 metre grid reference for privacy reasons (see below)

These questions were intended to allow exploration of the interaction between location, nature of activity, visual stimuli, sound exposure and the participants' perception of their general and sound environment.

These momentary assessments were supplemented by reflective questionnaires delivered at the end of a week, end of weekend and on completion of the survey trial, which gathered data on:

End of week/weekend:

- Impact of sound environment on wellbeing
- Impact of landscape on wellbeing
- Extent to which week/weekend had been typical

Final:

- Impact of sound environment on wellbeing over experiment
- Impact of landscape on wellbeing over experiment
- Extent to which period was typical
- Sensitivity to noise
- Quality of life during study [using standard Personal Wellbeing Index (PWI) questions, please see Annex 8.2 for further details]
- Mood during study [using standard WHO-5 questions, please see Annex 8.2 for further details]

Once the questionnaire elements had been agreed the next challenge was to incorporate them into a mobile app that would allow self administration and automatic data capture.

4.1.2. Phase One Stage(ii) - Development of the App

The development of the app in two operating systems allowed its widespread use with the vast majority of modern smartphones in order to keep participation requirements at the lowest possible threshold. For the use of the AnimApp on these two systems, several operation system specific adaptations and adjustments were applied.

In regular field studies, the procedure of the study is explained in detail to the participants and once they agree to participate, they tend to comply well, which can be encouraged by offering an incentive. But with mobile applications, long text-based explanations, which might demotivate participants from participating need to be avoided. Concerted effort was made to formulate precise and succinct instructions.

Another challenge was how to maximise the likelihood that a user would indeed engage with the app, when the initial trial suggested that they may disregard notifications or prompts to do an assessment. After the pre-test phase, the decision was taken to allow 20 minutes' delay between notifications and potential answers, and to send reminder notifications every 5 minutes during the waiting period to the user.

The regularity of data provision was also considered: on the one hand, apps should avoid running all the time in the background (and thus draining battery) but, on the other hand, they need to send assessment data to the research server, once a measurement is completed. In this case, when connectivity was not available after a measurement had been made, there was no other option than to schedule data sending for a later time. However, efforts were made to ensure phone battery charge drain was minimised and, even if the application was closed down by the user, the schedule for the upload of data still remained.

Finally, tracking of a participant's location posed further potential difficulties. The study was designed to require the position of the user at the time of the assessment to be captured, so that an estimate could subsequently be made of the aircraft noise exposure for the respective position afterwards. In addition, participants were asked to allow tracking of their position all the time to help the researchers obtain an impression of how residents near airports move during the day (i.e. to understand – based on noise maps – how much they are exposed to aircraft vs. other noise). This option needed the consent of the user.

Other important considerations in development of the AnimApp:

Randomisation

From the point of view of later statistical analysis, the method of randomising measure conditions or the order of stimuli presented to participants (here: time of day of measurement) is an appropriate way of minimising response biases.

Therefore, to assure good randomisation among assessment hours assigned to each participant, it was decided that for the AnimApp: (a) participants would perform an assessment at randomly selected hours (but through the overall test period, each hour would be assessed just once) each day 2-4 times depending on the user-dictated settings chosen during set up, (b) a 10 minute time-frame would be defined around full hours and then the exact time randomly selected in the resulting time span (e.g. between 7:55 and 8:05).

Data security and privacy

In the development of the AnimApp, several steps were taken to ensure people's privacy and to be fully compliant with GDPR (General Data Protection Regulations):

- It was not necessary for the users to enter any personal data to register for the study. They were simply given a randomly generated user ID to ensure that both users and their answers would remain anonymous.
- The sound recording on the phone was transferred into a series of 3rd octave band spectra, one for each second, and only this was transmitted to the server. This enabled privacy as the original audio recording could not be reconstructed from these acoustic data.
- The user had to explicitly agree to constant location tracking, and could also refuse to have it switched on, if preferred. Also, positions were rounded to a grid of 100 * 100 m on the user's phone and only then sent to the server.
- On initial use, a participant had to explicitly agree to the privacy policy, including an agreement that the researchers could collect/store/process data from the participant with his/her consent.
- Due to data security and privacy considerations, as well as difficulties in later objective assessment, while it had been initially anticipated that participants would be asked to take pictures to allow assessment of their visual environment, a decision was made to not make this request of app users.

Languages

Two different sized airports were chosen for the app experiment, Ljubljana Airport in Slovenia, and London Heathrow Airport in the UK. Thus, the application was made available in English and translated into Slovenian.

4.1.3.Phase One Stage(iii) - Preliminary testing and feedback

An initial version of the application was tested during winter of 2018/19 in Slovenia and the UK, and a feedback questionnaire was issued to the "beta" testers during that period. This highlighted some questions lacking clarity in the language used and also areas where app functionality could be improved.

4.2. Phase Two – Release Phase Methodology

4.2.1. Phase Two Stage(i) – Refinement of the test method

Drawing on the findings from Phase One, the questions contained in the app were refined for clarity and use of language to enhance understanding by users. This resulted in modifications to app content and performance which are captured in the following final app specification and operational guidance.

4.2.2. Phase Two Stage (ii) App modification and release to app stores

This section provides an overview of the app's operation and the guidance given to participants. The detailed app specifications are provided in the Annex 8.1. and the variables examined are described in the survey results section (5).

Once a participant had agreed to take part in the trial, they were given instructions on how to download and use the app. For example, in the UK, the following email was sent to the participant:

Thank you again for offering to take part in the trial of the ANIMA app.

It is no problem if your notifications are turned off at certain times of the day. During the set up of the app, you will be able to specify the period in which you are happy to answer the survey.

Here are a few instructions to get you started. Using your mobile phone, please click on this link <https://anima-project.eu/noise-platform/animapp> to access further information about the app. Please then use the links at the top of the webpage which will take you to your respective iPhone or Android store where the app can be downloaded.

Once you have downloaded the app, it will guide you through the set-up procedure during which you will be asked to enter your UserID. Your unique ID is 123456.

You will then be asked to answer a questionnaire through the app a few times a day. I hope that you find the instructions on the app helpful. If you have any problems or queries, just contact me by email.

The following images in Figure 2 capture the various information screens guiding the participant during the app set up:

Figure 2: Images of app set up information

Once participants had downloaded the app and performed the set-up procedures noted above, they were ready to start using the app. An aural prompt was used to indicate to the participant that a survey was due to be completed. If there was no response to the prompt, the app would repeat the sound up to 4 times for the survey to be completed at that time. If the participant still had not filled in the survey, the app would prompt them on another day at the same time to see if they could then interact with it.

Once a prompt had been received, the participant was asked to make a 1-minute recording to capture their sound environment. On completion of the recording, the participant was then asked to fill in the momentary questionnaire through the app. The questions asked can be found in the Annex 8.2.

4.2.3. Phase Two Stage(iii) – Participant recruitment

There was a mix of approaches to recruitment adopted in Slovenia and the United Kingdom. Each of the methodologies is described below.

Recruitment methodology: Slovenia – Ljubljana Jože Pučnik Airport

Initial approach: Written invitations

Sample of participants

A sample of participants was prepared by the Central Population Register at the Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia for the survey.

The population from which the sample was drawn includes people aged from 18 to 60 years on 1 January 2021. The sampling plan provides a stratified random sample in selected municipalities, with municipality as stratum. The Slovenian sample consists of 630 residents. The sample included people from the municipalities of Cerklje na Gorenjskem, Domžale, Komenda, Kranj, Mengeš, Šenčur and Vodice. A total of 90 people, 45 men and 45 women, were selected

from each municipality, and these represented a proportional distribution of ages from 18 to 60 years.

Invitations

All invitees received a code to input to the web application to ensure the anonymity of individuals. The invitation to participate included a contact number, email for support and/or any queries about the survey and a link to the online instructions for using the AnimApp.

Instructions for using the Anima Research mobile application

We prepared and published detailed instructions for using the mobile application on the website of the National Institute of Public Health (NIJZ) <https://www.nijz.si/sl/animapp>.

Supplementing the sample – Advertising the mobile app

The invitation to the survey AnimApp was additionally published on the NIJZ website (available on the website: <https://www.nijz.si/sl/animapp>) and on the social networks Facebook and Twitter due to poor response from invited citizens. In addition, the invitation was sent by e-mail to all employees of the NIJZ and the National Laboratory for Health, Environment and Food (NLZOH) living near Ljubljana Airport. The invitation was also sent to all stakeholders at Ljubljana Airport and to all six municipalities near Ljubljana Airport. Throughout the research, we personally invited friends and relatives with permanent residence in the vicinity of the airport to participate. On 24 June 2021, the invitation to participate was also extended to the inhabitants of the Gorenjska region by the journalists of the newspaper Gorenjski Glas with a publication in their newspaper, and on 28 June 2021 on their website (Stanovnik, 2021).

Response information

After the distribution of invitations, three phone calls and two emails were received. Seven invitations were not delivered and therefore returned to our address. Phone calls and emails related to the fact that two people did not have a smartphone, one person would prefer to complete the survey in person via telephone conversation, one person needed further explanation of the aim of the study, and one person refused to participate in the survey due to cell phone use, location tracking, unforeseen amounts of time for completing surveys, and frequent disruption of work rhythm and concentration.

Residents responded to post on the social media Facebook with total 95 comments and 7 shares of the post. The comments were negative and related to the COVID situation, as the NIJZ is involved in advising on measures to contain the COVID pandemic. Of all the comments, only two commented on the survey itself.

Analysis of the experiences of participants with the ANIMA research mobile application in Slovenia

After the AnimApp survey was finished an online questionnaire was set up using the 1KA survey program to evaluate the experiences with the mobile application that participants had during the AnimApp survey.

The 1KA survey was activated by a total of 19 persons in the period from 5-18 October 2021 and finished by 11 persons.

Of the 11 people, ten participated in the AnimApp survey.

The reasons the ten respondents gave for participating in the AnimApp survey were:

- contributing to scientific research
- helping young scientists
- being part of a regional research in the Kranj area
- feeling honoured by the invitation
- being affected by/exposed to noise in the surroundings

Only one person had trouble downloading the Anima Research mobile app to their mobile phone. The person also had problems continuing to launch the app, recording audio, and also did not receive notifications to complete the momentary surveys. The person sought help in the online instructions for using the mobile application, but did not perceived them as useful and indicated that they felt that the research was too complicated. This participant did not seek other help from the organisers of the survey.

Nine persons had no problems downloading the mobile app, also did not mention any further problems, except for one person who said that the app did not work towards the end and did not have to answer the last questions, so the person deleted the app, reloaded and closed the survey.

Recruitment methodology: United Kingdom – Heathrow Airport and beyond

It was initially anticipated that people living in the vicinity of Heathrow Airport would be recruited to participate in the app trial. The intention was for researchers to approach people in their homes in specific areas, delineated by sound exposure, and ask them to take part. Or, alternatively, to use a leaflet drop in these areas to encourage participation. Due to the COVID pandemic lockdown rules in the UK, it was not possible for anyone to be approached face-to-face or for researchers to travel, even for work purposes. Over the months of lockdowns, the research team discussed other ways of recruiting, including approaching people in supermarkets and other facilities, when restrictions were slightly eased. But the rules were not sufficiently changed to allow travel or to enable a researcher to be within 2 metres of another person.

A more hands off method was then adopted, approaching organisations active in the relevant areas of sound exposure (areas of relatively low - $<60 L_{den}$ - and high - $> 65 L_{den}$ - aircraft noise exposure under take-off and landing paths had been

identified), to ask if people would be willing to take part. Approaches via local organisation emails/contacts in the Heathrow area did not yield any responses. It was then decided that Twitter would be used and invitations were posted to 27 accounts of organisations active in the relevant locations. In addition, as it was becoming clear that a large sample would be impossible to obtain, a decision was made to also seek participation via two large amenity groups, HACAN (Heathrow Association for the Control of Aircraft Noise) and AEF (Aviation Environment Federation). The initial Twitter campaign yielded two participants. The AEF contact resulted in 18 offers to participate. However, as the AEF is not Heathrow-specific, some of the people coming forward were found to be located nearer to other UK airports (Gatwick, Leeds Bradford). The HACAN request did not result in anyone expressing interest in participation. A further Twitter recruitment round was run, yielding only two more participants.

Given such a low level of response, it was decided to try to recruit around Manchester Airport, relying on local links given the University's location. Recruitment focused on the East and the West of the airport, with recruitment to the East being driven by social networks, website, newspaper and Twitter posts. To the West, parents at a school (with a benevolent headteacher) in an overflowed area were asked if they would be willing to help with the trial. The overall Manchester recruitment resulted in 18 participants.

It should be noted that incentives (£20 Amazon vouchers) were offered in the invitation to non-amenity group participants if they completed the trial.

4.2.4. Phase Two - Stage (iv) - Conducting the field study and response statistics

The challenges in recruiting participants were reflected in the final sample which was limited to 47 across both country locations. Their participation resulted in the collection of a total of 968 momentary assessments across both weekdays and weekends (see Table 1). It should be noted that these participants used the app during a period (June-July 2021) in which air traffic volumes were profoundly affected by COVID travel restrictions, meaning that the **collected data cannot be regarded in any way as reflective of the normal lived experience of residents living near airports**. Rather we present data and subsequent analysis in order to reflect on the utility of the app and its capacity to generate information that can be used to explore the relationships between location, activity, visual stimuli and the perception of the general and sound environment. Before presenting this analysis it is worth making a few more observations on the dataset as a whole.

Examination of the momentary assessments provided by participant groups according to different categories illustrates that engagement with the app was not consistent (with some participants failing to complete the full diet of momentary assessments and also those reflective assessments at end of week, end of weekend and end of survey that yield data on age, gender and noise sensitivity). This is reflected in the population of momentary assessments categorised by

location, gender, age and noise sensitivity (please see Table 1). As might be expected, the distribution of momentary assessments across some of these categories limited some of the possible cross-tabulations in the analysis that follows.

Table 1: Summary of app users and the momentary assessments collected in various categories

Categories	Attributes	Participants	Momentary assessments (MA)	Weekday MA	Weekend MA
Location	Total	47	968	675	293
	Slovenia	26	530	363	167
	UK	21	438	312	126
Gender	Total	34	715	496	219
	Male	8	169	120	49
	Female	26	546	376	170
	Other	0	0	0	0
Age	Total	34	715	496	219
	18-24	2	35	21	14
	25-34	9	189	131	58
	35-44	9	199	141	58
	45-54	9	187	130	57
	55-64	3	60	42	18
	65-74	2	45	31	14
Noise sensitivity	Total	31	666	464	202
	Not at all sensitive	1	24	17	7
	A little sensitive	5	114	81	33
	Moderately sensitive	11	234	161	73
	Fairly sensitive	8	161	111	50
	Very sensitive	6	133	94	39

When momentary responses are classified by the location and nature of the activities in which participants were engaged at the time of completing the questionnaire, it is also evident that there are very few assessments in some categories, which again prevented any statistically meaningful correlations between these features and the perceptions of the environment recorded.

Table 2 indicates that for many activities [both at the broader level shown in Activity (a) and at the more specific level – Activity (b)], there were very few momentary assessments in a number of categories. Indeed, given the number of momentary responses and their distribution by activity, analysis could only be focused on location, whether indoors or outdoors.

Table 2 – Distribution of momentary assessments across the nature and location of activities

	Indoors/ outdoors	Activity(a)	Activity(b)	Momentary assessments	Weekda y MA	Weeken d MA		
At home	Indoors		Housework	96	55	41		
			Internet browsing/TV	136	79	57		
			Resting	84	54	30		
			Talking	25	23	2		
			Concentrating/readin g	116	103	13		
			Eating	34	23	11		
			DIY	3	2	1		
			Physical activity/sport	8	6	2		
		Other....	44	32	12			
	Total at home indoors				546	377	169	
	Outdoors			Talking	29	17	12	
				Concentrating/readin g	14	8	6	
				Internet browsing/TV	21	13	8	
				Gardening	24	16	8	
				Resting	22	13	9	
			DIY	9	4	5		
			Physical activity/sport	5	4	1		
Total at home outdoors				142	88	54		
Not at home	Indoors	At work	Communicating	32	32	0		
			Concentrating/readin g	40	39	1		
			Physical activity/ manual work	8	8	0		
			Meal/break	5	4	1		
			Other....	3	3	0		
		At school/ university	Communicating	1	1	0		
			Concentrating/readin g	1	1	0		
			Physical activity/sport	0	0	0		
			Meal/break	0	0	0		
			Other....	1	1	0		
		Shopping/ personal care				8	6	2
		Leisure activity	Talking	10	4	6		
			Concentrating/readin g	0	0	0		
			Resting	7	3	4		
			Cinema/concert...	1	1	0		
			Physical activity/sport	5	4	1		
	Other...	2	1	1				
Travelling				12	8	4		
Other....				17	12	5		
Total not at home indoors				153	128	25		
Outdoors	At work	Communicating	3	3	0			

			Concentrating/reading	2	2	0	
			Physical activity/manual work/sport	2	2	0	
			Meal/break	1	1	0	
			Other.....	2	2	0	
		At school/university	Communicating	3	3	0	
			Concentrating/reading	0	0	0	
			Physical activity/sport	0	0	0	
			Meal/break	0	0	0	
		Leisure time	Other.....	0	0	0	
			Talking/visiting/meal	24	8	16	
			Festival/leisure park	1	0	1	
			Resting	3	2	1	
			Shopping	1	0	1	
			Physical activity/sport	7	4	3	
		Travelling	Other...	3	1	2	
			Countryside	11	4	7	
			Main road	9	8	1	
			Urban streets	6	6	0	
			Urban park	3	3	0	
			Pedestrian street	1	1	0	
			Market place	0	0	0	
			High street/retail park	2	2	0	
		Other....	2	2	0		
		Other....	41	28	13		
		Total not at home outdoors			127	82	45

The distribution of momentary assessments across such a large number of location and activity categories not only reflects the influence of COVID restrictions on movement but also suggests that a much larger sample of participants would be required to ensure the levels of representation in all categories required for meaningful statistical analysis. Given the challenge of recruitment already described, a more generalised description of activity/location has been used in some of the analyses detailed below (i.e whether the participant was indoors or outdoors).

4.2.5. Phase Two – Stage (v) Data analysis

Given the limitation in the data sample outlined above and, more crucially, an acknowledgement that the app was deployed during an exceptional period of air transport disruption caused by COVID management interventions by nation states, the analytical steps and outcomes described below are for illustrative purposes only. Therefore **the aim is only to highlight the capacity of the app to yield useful data from which the relationship between individuals and their soundscape can be explored.**

5. Suggested survey analyses and illustrations

5.1. Introduction

Study circumstances

The AnimApp survey was conducted in an unusual situation, namely, in the summer of 2021 during the COVID pandemic, when the traffic in the airport regions under study was still reduced and people's activities indoor and outdoor were thus expected to differ from the time period before the pandemic. Therefore, any generalisation of the results of this survey regarding the perception of the sound environment indoor and outdoor should be done with caution, in particular, when it comes to any recommendations regarding aircraft noise management. Further, with 47 participants, less people than intended could be recruited limiting the number of measurements and, thus, the power of the statistical analysis.

Therefore, it was decided, not to present results of statistical analysis and interpret them as evidence for recommendations for aircraft noise management, but, instead, illustrate, which statistical analyses could be done with the collected data and how the results could be presented. That is, this section 5 provides examples of the types of statistical analysis and results that can be obtained guiding future studies conducted with the AnimApp.

Relations between end of week evaluations and momentary assessments are presented in Chapter 5.3 followed by illustrative results of the associations between momentary assessments and responses in the final questionnaire, described in Chapter 5.4. The following section 5.2 illustrates results of the momentary assessments.

Questionnaires

The Codebook summarises all questions that were included in the AnimaApp survey (Annex 8.2). Sets of questions for momentary assessments were the same for weekdays and weekends. Reflective questions were then asked at the end of each week and after the weekends. At the end of study, participants had to answer more general and demographic questions in the final questionnaire.

Data analysis

General analysis of data was primarily done for the questions regarding the perception of the sound environment. It is followed by analysis of data for questions that would clarify differences in reactions of participants to the sound environment during the survey. More detailed statistical analyses were performed in cases where such differences were expected or would be of particular interest within the ANIMA project. Furthermore, examples are given on how to relate the momentary assessments (sound perception and acoustic metrics) to reflective responses at the end of the week and in the final questionnaire at the end of the survey (for example, we considered the self-rated noise sensitivity, against quality of life measured using the PWI and the WHO scores).

Database structure

The complete database includes all responses made during the survey by 47 participants and sound data from recordings performed by the application during the survey and aircraft noise data modelled for the location and time for each participant and momentary assessment. The database was structured according to the questionnaires in four parts, collecting responses for:

- all momentary evaluations registered during all week and weekend days (momentary database),
- overall reflective evaluations for the past week days (end of week database),
- overall reflective evaluations for past days during all weekends (end of weekends database) and
- final reflective responses at the end of the study also including demographic information (final database).

Selected variables for evaluation

The following variables were evaluated for general presentation of responses in the survey. The answers were selected on a 11-point differential semantic scale or among suggested options for questions about activities at home indoor (homeIn) and outdoor (homeOut):

- Sound pleasantness (soundPleasant): Specifically, how would you describe the SOUND environment of your current location? unpleasant (-5) ... pleasant (+5)
- Sound eventfulness (soundEventful): Specifically, how would you describe the SOUND environment of your current location? uneventful (-5) ... eventful (+5)
- Impact of the sound on any activity being undertaken at the time of the survey (soundImpact): How is the impact of the sound environment on the activity you were engaged in? distracting (-5) ... supportive (+5)
- Pleasantness of the overall environment (pleasant): OVERALL, how would you describe your current environment? unpleasant (-5) ... pleasant (+5)
- Eventfulness of the overall environment (eventful): OVERALL, how would you describe your current environment? uneventful (-5) ... lively (+5)
- Familiarity of the overall environment (familiar): OVERALL, how would you describe your current environment? unfamiliar (-5) ... familiar (+5)
- Location (where): Are you ... (1) at home, indoor, (2) at home, outdoor, (3) not at home, indoor (enclosed space), (4) not at home outdoor (in an open area)
- Activity at home, indoor (homeIn): What have you just done before responding to this round of questions? housework (1), internet browsing/watching TV/listening to music or radio (2), resting / quiet contemplation (3), talking (4), concentrating / desk work / reading (5), eating a meal (6), home improvement / do-it-yourself work (7), physical activity, sport (8) and other: (9).

- Activity at home, outdoor (homeOut): What have you just done before responding to this round of questions? Talking (1), reading, concentrating (2), internet browsing / watching TV / listening to music or radio (3), gardening (4), resting / quiet contemplation (5), home improvement / do-it-yourself work / car washing (6), physical activity, sport (7) and other: (8).

Statistical tools

For the data analysis we used the two statistics software packages; Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), Version 27, and R, Version 4.1.2.

5.2. Momentary data assessment

The momentary data includes all judgements from all participants during the weekdays and weekends. For the analysis of the momentary data with repeated measures of multiple respondents we suggest multiple response analysis, Generalized Estimating Equations (GEE) analysis and repeated measure correlation analysis.

Multiple response analysis is a frequency analysis for data which includes more than one response per participant. Multiple response analysis allows the set of responses to be combined and collectively analysed. This analysis illustrates the frequencies and percentages by cases and responses. We can obtain the information about how many persons gave a specific response and how many times a response was given.

Generalized Estimating Equations (GEE) analysis is used to estimate differences in outcome responses between subgroups of the sample, considering both within-subject factors, i.e. factors that specify repeated measurements of a respondent, and between-subject factors, i.e. factors that characterise different subgroups of respondents. The focus of the GEE is on estimating the average response over the population ("population-averaged" effects), which tells us whether group differences are statistically significant or not.

With repeated measure correlation analysis ($r(rm)$) the combined linear relationship between pairs of measures and responses within a subject and between subjects is quantified. The analysis takes into account that a sample of persons repeatedly did assessments over a period of time, therefore, leading to data with a mixture of dependent measures (several measures of a person) and independent measures (measures of multiple individuals).

5.2.1. Multiple responses analysis

In our study, multiple responses analysis was used to assess the frequencies of momentary evaluations by number of persons responding and by type of response selected. The analysis was performed for the selected variables: soundPleasant, soundEventful, soundImpact, pleasant, eventful, familiar, where, homeln and

homeOut in general and specifically with consideration of different country, gender, age and noise sensitivity of participants. The distinction was made for responses obtained during the weekdays and weekend. Illustrative examples of the types of presentation that can be made are given in Figures 3-8 below:

Figure 3: In general, participants evaluated the sound environment more frequently as pleasant compared to unpleasant during the weekdays as well as during the weekends.

Figure 4: The judgements of sound pleasantness considering the age of participants or their sensitivity to noise. Results summaries the responses during the weekdays.

Figure 5: Different responses of sound eventfulness judged between two extremes, uneventful and lively, considering the country or age of participants.

Figure 6: Judgements for sound impact considering participants from all noise sensitivity categories separately and when grouped in three categories: all responses judged towards distracting, neutral responses and all responses incliden towards suportive.

Figure 7: Judgements of overall environmental pleasantness, eventfulness and familiarity during the weekdays.

Figure 8: Engagement in diverse activities during the weekdays and weekend.

5.2.2. Detailed observations for combined variables after the Generalized Estimating Equations (GEE) correlation analysis

With GEE analysis we intended to identify significant differences among sets of selected data (subgroups). This was done for the following variables: soundPleasant, soundEventful, soundImpact as dependent variables and independent variables: homeIn, homeOut, country, gender, age, where (home or not at home indoor or outdoor) and noise sensitivity.

Age

- soundPleasant: The judgements belonging to the group of the youngest participants are significantly higher for pleasantness of sound compared to the groups 25-34 and 45-54 years old. This is more pronounced at the weekend than on weekdays.
- soundEventful: On weekdays, the sound environment is increasingly judged as uneventful with increasing age. This result is less obvious for judgements at the weekend.
- soundImpact: Responses for age category 18-24 years old suggest higher supportive impact of sound on any activity being undertaken compared to responses in age groups 25-34 years old and 45-54 years old. However, as this age group is represented by only two people, the results are solely shown for illustration (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Sound environment is judged in general as uneventful and lower with increasing age. Sound impact is judged lower with age without remarkable difference between weekdays and weekends.

Noise sensitivity:

The data generated by the app allows relationships between noise sensitivity and sound perception to be explored. However, in this deployment, the distribution of individuals across noise sensitivity categories was very uneven and so the following comments are made to demonstrate the potential of the app to reveal relationships rather than to imply that these relationships are robust in this case.

- soundPleasant: Data for sound pleasantness, there is no statistically significant relationship with noise sensitivity categories.
- soundEventful: There is a linear decrease in judgement of sound eventfulness with increasing noise sensitivity. Significant difference is observed between the responses of most sensitive group compared to fairly and very sensitive group.
- soundImpact: Significant differences across noise sensitive groups were observed, however, this might be a result of the differences in group size.

Where (at home/not at home, indoor/outdoor):

- soundPleasant: Significant difference was noticed for sound pleasantness judgement between those at home outdoors and those not at home indoors.

- soundEventful: The sound environment was judged more lively when not at home than when at home and the difference was even bigger when outdoors.
- soundImpact: The sound environment was judged as less supportive when participants were indoors but not at home compared to other situations (inside or outside at home or outdoors elsewhere).

HomeIn (activities at home, indoors):

- soundPleasant: There is no difference in sound pleasantness indoor at home in dependency of the activity done during the survey.
- soundEventful: Significant difference in sound eventfulness judgment is the greatest when people are engaged in home improvement/do-it-yourself work compared to people resting.
- soundImpact: When people were at home they judged the sound impact during different activities they were engaged in at the time of interruption for the survey. Those involved in home improvements judged the sound has having no impact on their activity, which was the only category that differed statistically from the others.

HomeOut (activities at home, outdoor):

- soundPleasant: For activities at home outside, the sound pleasantness during different activities differs between weekdays and weekend. For most activities, the sound outside at home is more pleasant at the weekend rather than on weekdays. Further detailed differences in sound pleasantness between activities at weekend and weekdays are hard to interpret due to low absolute number of persons and judgments per activity.
- soundEventful: Significant difference in sound eventfulness judgment is found between situations when people are engaged in home improvement/do-it-yourself work/car washing (6) compared to situation when they are reading, concentrating (2) and also to situations when they spend time resting/quiet contemplation (5). Judgements of the eventfulness of the sound environment differ between activities on weekdays and during the weekend and are more 'extreme' on weekdays than during the weekend. For example, on weekdays the sound is judged as uneventful during reading/concentration and as lively during passive communication (watching TV, listening to music/radio). It seems obvious that the judgements of the sound eventfulness differ between activities, in particular if one assumes the sound of one's own activity (e.g. listening to music) to be part of the evaluated sound environment. However, at the weekend these judgements are more between these poles of eventfulness. The reason for the difference in judged sound eventfulness between types of day (weekday/weekend) is unclear.
- soundImpact: There is no difference in the perceived impact of the sound environment at home outdoor on the activities being undertaken.

5.2.3. Associations of momentary assessments with the evaluation of the momentary sound environment

The assessments during the momentary measurements regarding

- the perception of the environment,
- the mood,
- the acoustic metrics derived from the recordings with the AnimApp,
- and the modelled aircraft noise exposure metrics

were correlated with perceptual judgments of the sound environment, i.e. with pleasantness and eventfulness of the sound environment, and its impact on current activities.

As the data of the momentary assessments include for each participant responses, recordings and calculated aircraft noise metrics ('variables') of repeated measurements, a correlation coefficient was calculated that considers both, the correlation of variables within a subject and between subjects. This is the repeated measures correlation $r(rm)$ which determines "the common within-individual association for paired measures assessed on two or more occasions for multiple individuals." (Bakdash & Marusich, 2017, p. 1).

Table 3 shows the results for the correlation between the evaluation of the sound environment with various survey variables and acoustic metrics. The complete table with all correlation analyses can be found in Annex 8.6.

The main results depicted in Table 3 and illustrated in Annex 8.5 are summarized below:

- The evaluation of the sound environment is related to the evaluation of the environment (including the visual landscape) in general and to the current mood.
 - The more the sound environment is judged as pleasant, the more the environment at the participant's location is judged as pleasant, uneventful and – although more weakly related to each other – as familiar, and the better the momentary mood of the respondents.
 - The more the sound environment is evaluated as lively, the less the environment in total is judged as pleasant and familiar, and the more it is judged as eventful/lively. The more the sound environment is judged as uneventful, the better the mood.
 - The more the overall environment is perceived as lively, the more the sound of the environment is regarded as distracting.
- The evaluation of the sound environment is related with most of the acoustic metrics derived from the recordings.
 - The more the recorded sound levels deviate in terms of higher levels from the average sound levels each participant is exposed to the less pleasant the sound is perceived. The relationship is strongest for the

- relative background levels $L_{90, \text{reSPL}}$ and $L_{90, \text{reAvg}}$. (For further information, please see Annex 8.4.
- The higher the relative sound levels, the more the sound environment is judged as being lively. This is in particular true (strongest effect) for $L_{A50, \text{reSPL}}$ and $L_{A50, \text{reAvg}}$.
 - The relationship between the relative sound levels from the recordings and the perceived impact of the sound environment on the activity being undertaken is, overall, ambiguous. For most of the relative sound level metrics, the association is negative, though quite weak in effect size, indicating more evaluation of the sound as being distracting with increasing relative sound levels. A much stronger and opposite relationship can be seen for the relative continuous equivalent sound levels $L_{\text{eq}, \text{reSPL}}$ and $L_{\text{eq}, \text{mid}, \text{uncal}}$. Higher relative L_{eq} levels are associated with stronger perception of the sound environment as being supportive of the activity being undertaken.
 - Finally, across all locations, times, activities and main sound sources perceived, there is almost no association between the evaluation of the sound environment and the outdoor aircraft noise exposure modelled for each momentary time and location.

Table 3: Repeated measures correlation $r(rm)$ between variables of perception of the sound environment and other survey variables and acoustic metrics

Variables	Sound pleasantness unpleasant ... pleasant		Sound eventfulness uneventful ... lively		Sound impact on activity distracting ... supportive	
	$r(rm)$	p	$r(rm)$	p	$r(rm)$	p
<i>Perception of environment in total, mood</i>						
pleasantness of environment	0,595	0,000	-0,214	0,000	-0,010	0,758
eventfulness of environment	-0,307	0,000	0,761	0,000	-0,236	0,000
familiarity of environment	0,108	0,001	-0,193	0,000	0,047	0,158
mood	0,443	0,000	-0,124	0,000	0,051	0,139
<i>Selected acoustic metrics from recordings</i>						
L90_reSPL	-0,215	0,000	0,435	0,000	-0,118	0,001
L90_reAvg	-0,212	0,000	0,445	0,000	-0,116	0,001
LA50_reSPL	-0,210	0,000	0,510	0,000	-0,110	0,002
LA50_reAvg	-0,202	0,000	0,509	0,000	-0,109	0,002
Leq_reSPL	-0,174	0,000	0,422	0,000	0,472	0,000
Leq_mid_uncal	-0,169	0,000	0,450	0,000	0,439	0,000
<i>Aircraft noise exposure</i>						
LAmx1min	-0,122	0,392	0,053	0,106	-0,039	0,267
LAmx10min	-0,068	0,500	-0,032	0,330	0,030	0,381

Variables	Sound pleasantness unpleasant ... pleasant		Sound eventfulness uneventful ... lively		Sound impact on activity distracting ... supportive	
	r (rm)	p	r (rm)	p	r (rm)	p
L _{Aeq} _10min	-0,051	0,493	-0,033	0,314	-0,065	0,063
L _{Aeq} _1min	-0,026	0,430	0,053	0,111	-0,069	0,048
nEvts10min	-0,025	0,451	0,004	0,893	-0,010	0,752
nEvts1min	-0,013	0,691	0,038	0,246	0,010	0,765

Highlighted variables and coefficients in bold and **Coloured font** indicate the highest two correlations in the column. A p-coefficients in light red indicates a non-significant correlation. The correlation coefficient r(rm) varies between -1 and 1 with values approaching the value 1 (-1) indicating higher positive (negative) correlation and values near 0 indicating low to no correlation. A negative bilateral correlation means that the higher the degree in one variable, the lower the degree in the other variable. A positive bilateral correlation indicates an increase in one variable with increasing values in the other variable.

Data presented in Table 3 can be illustrated graphically as in Annex 8.5 to aid interpretation. Repeated correlation plots are presented for a selected set of survey variables and acoustic metrics with evaluation judgments of the sound environment (sound pleasantness, sound eventfulness, impact of sound on acute activity).

Regarding the relationship between the momentary sound evaluations and the modelled aircraft noise exposure, in a next step, it was differentiated between situations where respondents mentioned aircraft noise as one of the outdoor sounds and situations where aircraft noise was not reported to be heard (Table 4).

Table 4: Repeated measures correlation r(rm) between variables of perceived sound environment and metrics of aircraft noise exposure in total and separate for situations with and without aircraft noise as perceived outdoor sound source

Variables	Total		Aircraft noise perceived		Aircraft noise not perceived	
	r (rm)	p	r (rm)	p	r (rm)	p
	Sound pleasantness unpleasant ... pleasant					
L _{Aeq} _10min	-0.051	0.493	-0.047	0.685	-0.019	0.593
L _{Aeq} _1min	-0.026	0.430	-0.160	0.168	0.0174	0.618
L _{Amax} 10min	-0.068	0.500	-0.043	0.710	-0.019	0.577
L _{Amax} 1min	-0.122	0.392	-0.161	0.164	0.0141	0.686
nEvts10min	-0.025	0.451	-0.038	0.745	-0.023	0.517
nEvts1min	-0.013	0.691	-0.137	0.238	0.021	0.548

	Sound eventfulness uneventful ... lively					
LAeq_10min	0.053	0.106	0.051	0.663	-0.041	0.241
LAeq_1min	-0.032	0.330	0.288	0.012	0.012	0.731
LAm _{ax} 10min	-0.033	0.314	0.050	0.671	-0.039	0.263
LAm _{ax} 1min	0.053	0.111	0.288	0.012	0.013	0.703
nEvts10min	0.004	0.893	0.107	0.357	-0.006	0.863
nEvts1min	0.038	0.246	0.257	0.025	0.004	0.917
	Sound impact on activity distracting ... supportive					
LAeq_10min	-0.039	0.267	-0.027	0.816	0.006	0.861
LAeq_1min	0.030	0.381	-0.020	0.867	0.006	0.871
LAm _{ax} 10min	-0.065	0.063	-0.021	0.855	0.007	0.850
LAm _{ax} 1min	-0.069	0.048	-0.023	0.846	0.003	0.932
nEvts10min	-0.010	0.752	0.055	0.637	-0.028	0.430
nEvts1min	0.010	0.765	-0.001	0.990	-0.007	0.832
	Number of observations					
Persons	47		23		24	
Measures	968		98		870	

A highlighted coefficient in **bold** indicates a statistical significant correlation. A p-coefficients in **light red** indicates a non-significant correlation. The correlation coefficient $r(rm)$ varies between -1 and 1 with values approaching the value 1 (-1) indicating higher positive (negative) correlation and values near 0 indicating low to no correlation. A negative bilateral correlation means that the higher the degree in one variable, the lower the degree in the other variable. A positive bilateral correlation indicates an increase in one variable with increasing values in the other variable.

Altogether, in 98 from 968 situations, 23 of the 47 participants reported having heard aircraft noise as one of the outdoor sound sources. In the subgroups, statistically significant correlations were only found for perceived sound eventfulness and the 1-minute continuous equivalent sound level $L_{Aeq,1min}$ and the 1-minute maximum sound level $L_{Amax,1min}$ in situations where respondents were aware of aircraft sound. The results indicate that with increasing $L_{Aeq,1min}$ and $L_{Amax,1min}$ the sound is evaluated as more lively in situations where respondents are aware of the aircraft sound. For other situations and other aspects of the perception of the sound environment, no significant relationship between aircraft noise exposure and judgments were found. In the total sample, only $L_{Amax,1min}$ significantly correlates with the perceived sound impact, but with low effect size, indicating that with increasing $L_{Amax,1min}$, the sound was judged as increasingly distracting.

5.3. Relations between End of Week evaluations and momentary assessments

This part aims to assess the variables that might influence the overall evaluation carried out by the participants at the end of the week(s) during the experiment. Please note, we only refer to end of week as there were too few observations to present end of weekend information.

The question asked is: Overall, what was the impact of the sound environment on your wellbeing over the week? The 11-points differential semantic scale is: [-5=Negative; +5=Positive].

The answers to this question creates a vector that we consider as the dependent variable. A volume of data was collected at each momentary assessment. We hypothesized that the momentary sound pleasantness assessments, as well as the sound impact assessments, influence the overall assessments.

In order to compare one EoW (End of Week) assessment with the preceding momentary assessments, some criteria have been defined:

1. Only the momentary assessments filled before the EoW assessment are taken into account;
2. One EoW observation is considered only if there are at least 4 momentary assessments filled by the participant in the last 5 days preceding the given EoW assessment (see Figure 10);
3. Only the momentary assessments collected up to 5 days before the EoW are taken into account in the analysis.

Since some of the participants filled two EoW questionnaires, there are in total 25 observations. 18 participants fulfill these criteria (13 from Slovenia, and 5 from United Kingdom). More details are described in Table 5.

Table 5: Description of the participants who filled at least one EoW assessment and who have filled at least 4 momentary assessment before the EoW questionnaire

Categories	Attributes	Participants	EoW assessments
Location	Total	18	25
	Slovenia	13	20
	UK	5	5
Gender	Total	18	25
	Male	2	2
	Female	16	23
	Diverse	0	0
Age	Total	18	25
	18-24	1	2
	25-34	6	9
	35-44	5	6
	45-54	5	7
	55-64	1	1
	65-74	0	0
Noise sensitivity	Total	18	25
	Not at all sensitive	1	1
	A little sensitive	3	4
	Moderately sensitive	7	11
	Fairly sensitive	1	1
	Very sensitive	6	8

We did not take into account whether the participant was inside or outside, neither his/her activity, because the number of observations was too small to allow a more detailed analysis. In order to study the influence between momentary assessments and EoW assessments, we calculated aggregated variables:

- Mean: average for each participant over the momentary assessments up to 5 days prior the EoW timestamp;
- Max: maximum recorded value per participant in the last 5 days prior the EoW timestamp;
- Min: minimum recorded value per participant in the last 5 days prior the EoW timestamp;
- Median: median over the momentary assessments up to 5 days prior the EoW timestamp;
- Last: the nearest momentary assessment before the EoW questionnaire.

Figure 10: Evolution of the momentary sound impact evaluation and the sound pleasantness evaluation compared to the EoW and the Final sound impact evaluations for userID 000189 (on left), and userID 000238 (on right).

In addition to the subjective data, some acoustic metrics have been collected at each momentary assessment: 1-minute recording with the mobile phone microphone, and some computed acoustic metrics (please see Annex 8.4 for further details). Based on the 1-min recordings of each momentary assessments, acoustic indicators were computed. The objective was to assess whether the EoW assessments were influenced by the acoustic indicators computed based on the third octave band spectra of 1 minute.

In total, 64 acoustic indicators have been calculated from the 1-min recording. In order to evaluate what are the most relevant indicators to study in the mixed model analysis, a Principal Component Analysis was first performed. This statistical analysis aims to select the most relevant acoustic metrics. Indeed, many acoustic variables are highly correlated to each other and the PCA aims to find a few groups of variables very correlated with each other within the group and the least correlated to the other groups (dimensions of the PCA are orthogonal). The acoustic dataset used for the PCA consists of as many variables (the columns) as acoustic computed indicators. The observations (the rows) are the individual momentary assessments. This PCA has been carried out with all the momentary assessments. Based on the PCA, we found three main factors (dimensions). For each of these three factors, we selected the most representative acoustic metric and, in total, we selected the following three metrics:

- SPL_std_reAvg ;
- L50_reAvg ;
- L90_uncal .

In addition, we completed the list with the Leq_mid_reAvg, and the L90_reAvg because a comparison between these two metrics with the same calibration method (based on the average spectrum) could be of interest.

A second acoustic dataset was developed based on the aircraft noise exposure for each momentary assessment. For the analysis, we considered the three acoustic metrics taking into account the last 10 minutes before the end time of the momentary assessment:

- nEvts10min: Number of flyover events during the 10 min time slot
- LAeq_10min: Equivalent Noise Level (dB(A)) due to the aircraft flyovers during the 10 min time slot
- LAmx10min: Maximum Sound Level (dB(A)) during the 10 min time slot due to aircraft flyovers.

For all the momentary acoustic metrics derived from the mobile phone recordings, aggregation has been performed with the same calculations as for the subjective data (i.e. extraction of the mean, min, max, median, and last).

Six variables have been considered:

- nEvts10min sum: Sum of all flyovers captured by ANOTEC for the momentary assessments considered in the analysis (i.e. all the momentary assessments per participant from 5 days before the EoW assessment up to the given EoW questionnaire;
- nEvts10min prop = nEvts10min sum / Number of assessments filled per participant before the given EoW questionnaire;
- LAeq,10min cumul: Logarithmic sum of all LAeq,10min captured by ANOTEC during the 5 day time slot before the EoW questionnaire;
- LAeq,10min mean = Arithmetic average of the all LAeq,10min captured by ANOTEC during the 5 day time slot before the EoW questionnaire;
- LAmx,10min cumul: Logarithmic sum of all LAmx,10min captured by ANOTEC during the 5 day time slot before the EoW questionnaire;
- LAmx,10min mean: Arithmetic average of the all LAmx,10min captured by ANOTEC during the 5 day time slot before the EoW questionnaire.

Finally, we hypothesized that non-acoustic factors describing the participants might have an influence on their overall end of week assessments. We considered the self-rated noise sensitivity of participants, against the quality of life using the PWI and the WHO scores, and computed the mean mood based on the momentary assessments responses.

In total, 46 models have been tested in considering the EoW soundImpact as the dependent variable, the userID as the random variable, and the momentary aggregated variables as the independent variables (see Table 6). All the independent variables have been firstly tested individually.

The variables written in green in Table 6 are those for which we found an influence in the mixed linear model (a tendency or a significance).

Table 6: List of the variables tested individually as an independent variable in the mixed linear model; the random variable being the userID, and the dependant variable being the EoW soundImpact.

Sensitivity to noise	LAeq,10min Cumul	L90_uncal median
Age	LAeq,10min Mean	L90_uncal min
Mood mean	nEvts10min Sum	L90_uncal max
PWI_sum	nEvts10min Prop	L90_uncal mean
WHO_sum	LAmx10min Mean	L90_uncal last
soundPleas median	LAmx10min Cumu	Leq_mid_reAvg median
soundPleas Max	SPL_std_reAvg median	Leq_mid_reAvg min
soundPleas Min	SPL_std_reAvg min	Leq_mid_reAvg max
soundPleas Last	SPL_std_reAvg max	Leq_mid_reAvg mean
soundPleas mean	SPL_std_reAvg mean	Leq_mid_reAvg last
soundImpact median	SPL_std_reAvg last	L90_reAvg median
soundImpact max	L50_reAvg median	L90_reAvg min
soundImpact min	L50_reAvg min	L90_reAvg max
soundImpact last	L50_reAvg max	L90_reAvg mean
soundImpact mean	L50_reAvg mean	L90_reAvg last
	L50_reAvg last	

In the Annex 8.6, a summary of the mixed models for which an influence of the independent variable has been found is presented.

The overall sound impact evaluated at the end of the week is highest correlated with the momentary sound impact median. It shows that participants were able to have a reflective assessment that takes into account the whole week and not only the worst situation (min sound impact or sound pleasantness), or the best situation (max momentary sound impact or pleasantness), or the most recent situation (last sound pleasantness or impact).

Second, the mean of the momentary mood assessments is correlated with the EoW sound impact. This result indicates that the mood of the participant has an influence on the perceived sound impact, indicating that the better the average of the momentary mood assessments the more positive, in the EoW assessment, a participant regards the influence of the sound on his/her wellbeing.

Regarding the acoustic indicators, there is only one acoustic metric for which a tendency was found: the Leq_mid_reAvg last. That would suggest that the end of week sound impact assessment is influenced by the equivalent sound level in the medium frequency range (from 200 Hz to 4 kHz) of the most recent momentary assessment before the end of week questionnaire. To confirm this result, we would need more datapoints because the relation is still weak (R^2 fixed factor = 0.14). Indeed, a simple regression which does not take into account the possible repetition has been carried out and was not found significant ($R=0.35$; p -value=0.1)

For each of the variables that have been found relevant based on the mixed model analysis, a linear regression has been plotted (See **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**).

Figure 21: Linear regressions to predict the end of week soundImpact variable. Regression coefficient R , Pearson p -value, and interval of confidence 95%.

For each of these independent variables, the regression coefficient is positive. To take the analysis further, more complex mixed models have been tested. First, we mixed both the mean mood variable and the median sound impact but the effects are not significant (See Annex 8.6, model 6). This failed attempt is probably due to the significant correlation between these two variables ($r=0.48$; p -value = 0.01), meaning that they cannot be independent from each other. The second

reason might be the insufficient number of observations available to compute the model (N obs=25).

Second, we included the mean of sound pleasantness judgments (per participant and per EoW questionnaire), and the acoustic metric Leq_mid_reAvg of the most recent momentary assessment preceding the EoW questionnaire as predictors in the model. We also tested a third mixed model in using the the sound impact median variable mixed with the Leq_mid_reAvg. Results of these models are presented in Table.

Table 7: Results of the mix linear models for evaluation of the factor that may influence the overall end of week sound impact assessments. The models 2, and 4 test the influence of both a perceptive variable (SoundPleas mean or SoundImpact median), with an objective acoustic metric (Leq_mid_reAvg last).

Fixed coefficients	Model 0	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Intercept	2.51(0.41 ; 6.16)***	0.78(0.52 ; 1.51)	0.07(0.62 ; 0.11)	0.25(0.84 ; 0.30)	-1.10(0.97 ; -1.14)
soundImpact median		0.75(0.19 ; 3.92)***	0.73(0.19 ; 3.88)***		
soundPleas mean				0.90(0.31 ; 2.89)**	1.04(0.32 ; 3.25)**
Leq_mid_reAvg last			0.05(0.02 ; 2.01).		0.06(0.02 ; 2.40)*
Pseudo R² Statistics					
R²Global	0.52	0.39	0.47	0.26	0.43
R²Pseudo Fixe-effect	0.52	0.39	0.47	0.26	0.58
Random parameters					
Participants	1.73(1.32)	0.00(0.00)	0.00(0.00)	0.00(0.00)	0.53(0.73)
Residual	1.61(1.27)	1.94(1.39)	1.80(1.34)	2.37(1.54)	1.50(1.23)
Goodness of fit					
AIC	103.9	95.7	93.7	99.5	94.7

Two models are able to describe the variance of the data:

- Sound Pleasant mean and Leq_mid_reAvg last;
- Sound Impact median and Leq_mid_reAvg last.

These models show that the overall weekly assessment of the sound impact is influenced by the sound environment of the last momentary assessment described by an equivalent sound level. The overall weekly assessment depends also on the mean sound pleasantness perception and on the median sound impact of the participants.

5.4. Relations between the final assessment and the momentary assessments

A description of the 31 participants who filled the final questionnaire is detailed in Table 8.

Table 8: Description of the participants who filled the final questionnaire

Categories	Attributes	Participants
Location	Total	31
	Slovenia	18
	UK	13
Gender	Total	31
	Male	7
	Female	24
	Diverse	0
Age	Total	31
	18-24	1
	25-34	8
	35-44	9
	45-54	8
	55-64	3
	65-74	2
Noise sensitivity	Total	31
	Not at all sensitive	1
	A little sensitive	5
	Moderately sensitive	11
	Fairly sensitive	8
	Very sensitive	6

A regression has been calculated to study the relation between end of week assessments and the overall final assessment of the sound impact. For the participants who filled two end of week questionnaires, an average over the two sound impact values was calculated first before computing the regression. The result of this regression is described in **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable..**

Figure 12: Regression curve comparing the influence between end of week assessments and the final assessments of the sound impact variable

One can notice the strong relationship between these two variables ($R=0.73$, Pearson p -value = 0.0004).

While we would have wished to then assess whether there are also some relations between the final assessments and the momentary responses, this was not possible: the mixed model cannot be used for this study because there is only one observation per participant (1 final questionnaire filled per participant). In order to use the mixed model with the participant IDs as a random variable, at least 2 observations per participant are needed (with possible missing values).

Therefore, in order to compare the momentary assessments with the final evaluation, we computed the correlations between aggregated momentary evaluations, and the final sound impact assessment. All the momentary assessments preceding the final questionnaire have been taken into account for the calculation. For this study, the dataset consists of 31 observations (18 participants from Slovenia, and 13 for the United Kingdom).

The same independent variables described in Table have been tested, and only the significant linear regressions are plotted below in **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.** with some details describing the linear regressions in Table 9.

Table 9: Description of the linear regression aiming to assess the relations between the final sound impact evaluation with momentary evaluations.

Variable name	R	Significance code or p-value
Mood mean	0.43	*
PWI sum	0.43	*
soundPleas median	0.38	.
soundPleas mean	0.35	.

soundImpact median	0.43	*
soundImpact mean	0.41	*

Compared to the relations found with the end of week assessments, we observe that the regression coefficients are lower. We could interpret this effect saying that the global rating after two weeks could be less dependent on momentary ratings than after one week, because of the memory which could depend on the experiment duration. Another explanation could be that in this regression, we include more momentary assessments (both weekday and weekend) adding to the heterogeneity of the sample.

Figure 13: Linear regressions to predict the Final soundImpact variable. Regression coefficient R , Pearson p -value, and interval of confidence 95%.

5.5. App usability

This sub-section looks at a number of factors related to the app's usability. This information was obtained via post-trial interviews with some of the UK participants and a survey of some of the Slovenian participants. While there was no intention

to capture views of a representative sample, the anecdotal responses served to provide insight into the app's utility.

Logistics:

While the app was reported to be easy to download (except by one respondent in Slovenia who also had problems launching the app, recording audio and receiving survey notifications), one participant commented on their discomfort with being asked to provide their location, stating that it felt invasive, and, thus, decided not to enable location tracking during the set up procedure.

In general, there were no problems with using the app. However, one participant suggested that they took 'a little while' to pick up the prompts to interact with the app. Another participant reported that the app did not appear to work towards the end of the trial and, therefore, they had not answered the final questions. Another participant had no issues in relation to app use but chose to control their interaction with it by disabling the prompts and, instead, set alarms for it to make it less invasive. In addition, some respondents suggested that the task of using the app was rather repetitive and/or laborious.

Influences on answers:

Participants' answers, and propensity to answer, were linked to factors such as the convenience of responding at the time of the prompt and their prevailing mood. For some, if they were with other people, they felt it inappropriate to interrupt their conversation, suggesting it may not have been ethical to record people they were with; or they chose to change location to be away from others, if they planned to answer the survey prompt. Others reported that, if they were in a busy location (e.g. supermarket) or fully engaged in another activity (e.g. lecturing), they may not have heard the prompt or, equally, may have chosen to ignore it due to the inconvenience of diverting their attention away from an important activity.

Mood was found to be an important influence on whether a participant was willing to respond to the app's prompt. A participant underlined this by suggesting that if they were 'feeling upbeat', they would be happy to answer. There was some indication that the repeated prompts could contribute to an irritability with respect to the app and an accompanied decreased likelihood to engage at a particular time.

Improving the app:

A manual override facility may be helpful: a participant expressed surprise that the timing of prompts was being controlled by the app, suggesting that they would have liked an ability to capture sound on demand at times they believed to be exceptional.

Clearer communications about how the sound file would be used would have aided understanding of privacy measures built into the app. Similarly, there was an indication that participants would have benefited from increased guidance on what to do in relation to the period of recording (i.e. the ability for participant to add a note about the sound environment such as 'immediately after the recording, I heard a spitfire overhead. It didn't bother me because I like that sort of plane'.)

Other learnings:

It was found that using the app potentially changes attitude to sound and it may also affect sensitivity to sound over time. For example, some participants reported that being part of the study had developed a greater awareness of the sound environment and that they had become more active listeners.

5.6. Discussion

The mobile application AnimApp was developed as a tool for a novel approach to evaluate the impact of the sound environment and other environmental and personal factors on wellbeing and quality of life of citizens living near airports.

An important part of the task was the development of the mobile application and its testing. Therefore, the information on the quality of this tool is an important result.

We incorporated both individual momentary assessment of the environment from different aspects and available acoustic data for aviation traffic.

This enabled the app to capture an important collection of multivariate data that could be beneficial for decision making in land use planning and management of aviation noise. However, the complexity of the data obtained requires careful analysis and interpretation of data.

The AnimApp survey was carried out as a pilot during the early summer of 2021 when COVID restrictions were in place. This was a time of reduced air traffic, and a period when the everyday life of people in the airport regions was different from that in non-pandemic times. Thus, the number of participants was lower than had been expected. Only a relatively small number of participants (47) fulfilled the minimum requirements for inclusion in the data analysis.

The reasons for such a small response can be attributed to a few factors. First, this was a new approach using mobile phones and not all citizens were familiar with using this type of application. Also, the length of the time commitment to complete the entire trial meant that there was a drop off of participants who had started the survey, but did not end up finishing it. In addition, recruitment to the trial proved challenging without the means to carry out face-to-face conversations to invite people to participate. The responses to survey invitations via other more

remote methods (such as letters and social media) were even less successful than usual during the pandemic conditions.

Nevertheless, the survey provided us with good information on functionality of the mobile application. Among participants who used the application and finished the survey there were no major complaints regarding its operation. Only minor corrections were suggested.

This survey also showed that a lot of diverse and important information can be gathered in a relatively easy novel way, which will hopefully become even more frequently used with new generations of citizens.

On the other hand, considering specific circumstances and the small data sample, the results of the data analysis presented have to be understood as representative illustrations of how the AnimApp data can be analysed.

Nevertheless, given that limitation, the momentary assessments have shown that the perception of the momentary sound environment in terms of pleasantness, eventfulness and the impact of the sound on respondent's activities differ

- by time, for example, type of day (weekday, weekend),
- context, such as location (being at home or not, being indoors or outdoors), and type of current activity during survey, and
- personal characteristics and dispositions such as age, noise sensitivity or the current mood.

The acoustic metrics derived from the recordings, as well as the modelled aircraft noise exposure data, seem, overall, to not be strongly associated with the personal evaluation of the sound environment. Obviously, context information is needed to understand the impact of momentary numbers and intensity of sound events on respondents. This would require subgroup analyses for the impact of sound exposure for different locations, times, activities, and types of sound. With the data available in the AnimApp survey such subgroup analyses were not possible given the relatively small sample size, for the reasons mentioned above; however, in the future such analyses could reveal much about the influence of these factors on sound perception.

Nevertheless, the data set did provide some insights into the role of the momentary context in determining the perception of the sound environment, which are in keeping with previous research on short-term annoyance or soundscape perception (e.g. Bartels et al., 2015; Schreckenber & Schuemer, 2010; Steffens et al., 2017).

Specifically, even with a limited number of participants in period of unusually low air traffic volumes, we were able to gather some interesting data which may suggest areas for further future exploration:

- Some relationships between perceptual data (sound pleasantness, sound eventfulness, sound impact on activity) and acoustic measurements have been revealed, showing that it is possible to explain a part of the perceptual evaluation variability with the acoustic recordings, even if mobiles were not calibrated.
- The different locations (indoors/outdoors; at home/not at home) and activities explain the variability in the perception of the sound environment.
- Mood is correlated with the sound pleasantness.
- The sound pleasantness is not evaluated independently from the overall eventfulness of the environment. Moreover, the link is negative showing that the more lively, the more unpleasant the sound environment.
- There are two aspects that explain almost 60% of the overall sound impact evaluation at the end of the week. These are the average of the momentary sound impact and sound pleasantness assessments and the relative equivalent sound level, measured at the location where the participant was for the last momentary assessment.

The findings of this pilot survey indicate the importance of understanding that in airport regions people's daily lives are dynamic including different places, times, moods, activities, and that this dynamism affects how people evaluate sound including the aircraft sound. The survey findings also show that the momentary assessments are not temporary, fleeting judgments, but that they contribute to medium- and, probably, long-term perception of people's sound environment.

Tools like the AnimApp are able to capture the dynamic daily life and the impact of the sound environment on it. Together with planning tools, such as the ANIMA dynamic noise maps (Ganić et al. 2020), they turn out to be potential instruments for providing useful information for comprehensive airport noise management.

6. Key learnings & recommendations for stakeholders

This research has sought to gain insights into the usability of the mobile phone based AnimApp, as a participative tool, for capturing instantaneous perceptions of the soundscape, including aircraft noise, when present.

The deployment of the application during a pandemic which caused unprecedented disruption to all forms of travel, including air transport, means that the findings cannot be viewed as representative of normal pre-pandemic life. Therefore, **it has only been possible to describe selected factors which may contribute to improved appreciation of how a mobile application may be used to understand the dynamic sound environment and to suggest ways in which the entire process of app deployment, use and analysis may be enhanced.**

6.1. Lessons learned

The AnimApp proved to be generally easy to use by participants who had been involved for the whole survey, indicating that this type of tool is a viable option for obtaining insights into people's experience of their soundscape. However, some citizens did not participate as they found the process too complicated, too long or they did not agree to being followed (using mobile phone GPS technology).

The app provided a technique for developing a comprehensive picture of perceived and measured experience to complement modelled data and enable more nuanced insights into lived experience of sound near airports. This aspect, in turn, means that there is potential within this type of application to inform airport operators, planning, political and other stakeholders about the impact of noise and other environmental and personal factors on wellbeing and quality of life of citizens living near airports. **Importantly, even in its present form, the app is suitable for the proposed purpose,** although further improvements may be useful.

6.1.1. AnimApp deployment

The major learning with respect to deployment relates to the challenges of recruitment. The trial suggested that **the use of personal social networks and connections was the most effective method for recruitment of participants** who then went on to complete the survey. Methods such as letters addressed to potential participants, invitations on Twitter and Facebook, and use of newspaper messages were much less successful. This may be attributed to a number of factors such as lack of face-to-face and/or personal interaction to explain the survey (imposed by COVID restrictions), low aircraft traffic volumes making the research seem irrelevant to the public, messaging via media which did not reach the main social groups in areas near airports, limitations on researchers' ability to visit locations where the public normally frequent (e.g. supermarkets,

post offices, mosques, community centres) and an absence of messages in commonly used non-native languages in airport neighbourhoods (in the UK).

To improve the number of participants, financial incentives were offered in the UK. However, these did not appear to influence people to take part.

In future, it is suggested that dedicated consultants be employed to recruit to specific social groups of interest to researchers. Such consultants have access to databases of members of the public and their attributes which would enable representative samples to be invited to participate. In addition, when face-to-face engagement is possible, long established social research techniques such as recruitment via conversations with people at key locations in their local area/at their homes can be re-established and augmented through snowball methods.

6.1.2. Using the app

As reported earlier, people found the application easy to use. Nevertheless, there are some aspects of the application that could be improved.

For most people, sufficient detail had been provided in the instructions to enable them to download and start using the application. Reflecting on reports of participants' experience with the application, we would suggest that participants be advised in the instructional materials to listen for the first few aural prompts to answer the questionnaires to avoid missing the initial sound notifications. It may also be helpful to highlight how the sound recording would be used even more clearly in the information given to participants. This would avoid people being concerned that the recording may in some way impact their privacy or anonymity. Given that some respondents found the trial rather repetitive, and to avoid attrition of numbers of participants, clear messaging about the time commitment being made is important. It may also be beneficial to incentivise participation over time through initiatives such as rewards for completing all weekday/weekend assessments, or more active researcher interaction over the two-week period of the survey to check in with participants and discuss any issues they may have.

Another consideration for future application development is the addition of functionality to allow participants to capture sound on demand when they feel it to be exceptional. This could add a richness to the data obtained and, perhaps, more realistically reflect how they react to their soundscape.

6.1.3. Data analysis

The pilot survey showed that a great amount and variety of data can be gathered. Considering all possible correlations of variables, it is clear that data analysis can be very demanding and complex. Therefore, **a step-by-step approach is needed and well specified questions that one wants to answer need to be**

selected. Circumstances and purposes of the research dictate which collection of data will be analysed and to what extent. In our study we provide a general presentation of frequencies of events and opinions, correlation between contextual elements such as location and time of week and variables like sound pleasantness, sound eventfulness and sound impact. Furthermore, **we were specifically interested in impact of aviation noise on citizens' judgement of their momentary mood and perception of their environment.** It is clear that evaluation of the present situation depends on several factors and cannot be explained only based on intensity level of even very loud sound events. It was shown that, at least for certain variables (for example, the most recent sound exposure had greatest influence over the reflective assessment of the sound environment – the recency effect), overall evaluation is in line with previous evaluations.

In addition, **it is important to ensure findings from the analysis are set in context.** Referring to mood, for example, while participants generally reported being in a good mood when answering the questionnaires, it would be incorrect to assume that this positive mood related to the app. A more nuanced explanation for mood needs to reflect on causation beyond the survey which recognises that extraneous factors (such as weather, light, and seasons) may have been affecting mood. It is considered likely that the participants would tend to answer when they were feeling positive, a type of self-fulfilling prophecy.

6.2. Conclusions

In comparison to traditional methods of exploring the sound environment around airports, this application enables more nuanced capture of the lived experience of the soundscape. The layers of information that are generated through the application, and through the analysis of its data with modelled data, contribute to greater insights into the dynamic nature of individual sound experience, in contrast to the static, time-bound nature of noise contours.

In addition, **the application enables an exploration of the relationship between soundscape and quality of life** – something that augments understanding for airport operators and allied stakeholders who are interested in managing the impacts of aircraft noise on communities.

The dynamic component of the application is particularly important to this contribution to knowledge about the experience of sound in various settings. Moving forward, we see this dynamism as central to improved understandings of local community experiences and point to the potential within dynamic mapping of increasing knowledge in this area (please see Ganić et al, 2020 for further details).

In summary, then, **the pilot study was a successful proof of the AnimApp concept** which showed that it can be used to collect important information that is crucial for a professional evaluation of noise impact on citizens. **It gives a clear indication that sound level is not enough to assess impact of sound on peoples' wellbeing and quality of life.** The AnimApp can be easily used and can give an opportunity to land use planners, decision makers and citizens to better understand and judge the environment where they live. As a result, we should expect better decisions for providing supportive and healthy living conditions near airports.

7. References

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8. Annex

8.1. App Specification

Basics of the Application

Momentary Assessments

- Assessments are performed 2 - 4 times a day, separately selectable for week and weekend days.
- Assessment times will be time slots around exact hours +/- 5 minutes, except the first and last examination hours, which are shifted by 5 minutes: i.e. 7:00-7:10, 7:55-8:05, ..., 21:55-22:00, 22:50 - 23:00
The app will randomly give a notification to do the assessment.
- The participant has 20 minutes from the appearance of the (first – see later) notification to START the assessment. (After 20 minutes, on Android the notification text will automatically change to an “OOUPS” text, on iOS the OOUPS will only come once the participant taps the notification or opens the app.)
- During the 20 minutes (survey late start) tolerance time the app will resend the notification (and give out the notification sound) every 5 minutes, i.e. at 0, 5, 10, 15 minutes as a reminder. (At 20 minutes, the start time is expired, so a new notification has no sense and will therefore not be sent.)
- If the participant doesn't start the assessment before the end of the tolerance time, then it will be rescheduled to another day. [Reason: on iOS it is not possible to find a replacement hour until the participant starts the app again (either by tapping the notification or by tapping on the app's icon)]
- During weekends: instead of 7:00-23:00, just 10:00-22:00 will be examined, and only every second hour: i.e. 10:05, 12:00, 14:00, ... 20:00, 21:55 +/- 5 minutes
- The gap between recording and advancing to first question MUST be less than 1 minute
- App interruption consequences: the overall test filling must be within 10 mins

End-of-week(end) Questionnaires

- A notification to perform a summary assessment after each work-week will be presented on Friday at **19:00**, and just one for weekends on the Saturday/Sunday-when the last weekend hour is completed.
- NO REPETITION of the notification.

- 1st EOW: the first momentary assessment should be by the latest on Wednesday, otherwise the end-of-week questionnaire will be sent the following week.
- EOWE: right after last weekend questionnaire, because -
 1. no reason to delay
 2. A fixed hour is not adequate as the last weekend examination can be even at 22:00, so any fixed hour earlier than that will cause to perform the EOWE only at the next weekend day, which can be almost 1 week behind
- THERE IS NO LIMIT on how late the participant can start to fill the end-of-week(end) questionnaire after the notification arrives, nor how long the participant can take to fill the three questions.

Final Questionnaire

- A notification to answer the final questionnaire is scheduled at 19:00 the day after
 - all week- and weekend-hours are completed **OR**
 - when the grace time is over (see below)
- Two reminder notifications are set 1 and 2 days after the first.
- "Major delay is included, when not completing the weekend hours". Therefore:
 - after 3 full weeks the app warns the participant that the 3 week limit is reached + gives the option to continue:

"We noticed that you were unable to complete the surveys in 3 weeks, which was foreseen by us. Would you like to continue for a further week or abort here and fill the final questionnaire now?"
 - If participant doesn't want to continue: final test **immediately**.
 - Otherwise a 1 week long "grace" period is started.
 - Once the grace period is over, the notification for the Final Test is scheduled for the day after at 19:00. (But the participant will not be notified.)
- THERE IS NO LIMIT on how late the participant can start to fill the final questionnaire after the notification arrives, nor how long the participant can take to fill the questions.

Other notes

- The request to perform an assessment/fill a questionnaire at a given time is driven by so called local notifications. (Like: new email message notifications.)
- Data sent from a particular participant to our server is identified by a user ID, which is fixed during first start/first data sending: either the participant enters it manually (if he/she has received one from us in an invitation letter/email and was asked to enter it) or if not entered, the app receives

automatically a user ID from the server during the first data sending session. The User ID cannot be modified later on.

- Audio data will be analysed for changes and not for absolute numbers.
- For privacy reasons, location data will be rounded to a 100x100m grid.
- In the app's information window, the number of remaining survey hours will be shown and listed

<p>upcoming survey hours = in the order they will come</p>	<p>remaining survey hours = not yet completed hours</p> <p>Today's survey hours = as they will (or were) – but ONLY today</p>

What to explain to participants in advance

It was decided that it would be best to introduce the participant to the test procedure during the door to door recruitment visits, however instructions will also be included in the app, so participants can re-read at any time. (Due to the deployment of the app being carried out during the COVID lockdown period, door to door recruitment did not take place and participants were introduced to the app through instructions in letters and emails).

- Test procedure

- Microphone position (top, bottom) on their phone, and how to hold the phone (mic away from the body), and to be quiet and not generate “mechanical” noise

Measurements should be performed in the location where the participant is at the moment of the examination (in-/outdoor)

- The app will send the data right after each examination, this takes less than 200KB each time, all together approx. 4 MB from participant’s mobile data plan. If mobile data is not available at that time, the app will send it later, when internet becomes available. (mobile or WiFi)

Additionally: in the app’s settings the use of mobile data can be completely be prohibited.

First Time Start

- Show the test procedure, which can also later be recalled (HELP)
- Prompt to agree to receive notifications. (Explanation that: “... When a survey time has come, the app will send you a notification. ...”)
- Prompt to agree to use microphone: “To take a sound recording, the app has to get your consent to do so. A popup window will appear to ask for it, please agree, otherwise the test cannot be fulfilled.”
- Prompt to agree to use location services:

“AnimApp needs to know your location, where you take the recording and fill out the questionnaires, so later, during analysis it can be related to nearby noise sources or unpleasant visual environment.

Location usage has to be explicitly agreed by the user, so please do so, when the requesting popup window appears.

In addition to the surveys, with your consent, we would like to continually follow your coarse (approx. 500 m precise) location, so we get an impression how much you were exposed to known traffic noise.

If you agree to this, please select “Always allow” on the popup window!

To protect your privacy, all collected location data will be rounded to a 100x100m grid, so your exact position will always remain hidden.”

- Prompt to agree our - GDPR compliant - privacy statement:
 - participating, including all the above-mentioned details (time period, location, etc)
 - storage of personal (contact) data (including explanation of pseudonymisation) for the scientific purpose of the ANIMA project until the end of the study or until withdrawal
 - AND storage of anonymised response data in general and storage of pseudonymised location and sound data for scientific research on residential living (or more specifically: noise effect research) in general.

Additional 'first time' items (note: the following settings can be changed at anytime in the settings):

- Prompt for survey hours separated for week- and weekend days: "We would like to survey you between 7 AM and 11 PM, once at each hour during the whole test. However we'd like to respect, if you normally get up later or go earlier to bed. If necessary, please make your modifications accordingly in the settings!"
Weekdays: A time selector: start hour selectable between 7 and 10, with default to 7; end hour selectable between 9 and 11 PM, with default to 11.
Weekends: A time selector: start hour selectable between 10 and 12, with default to 10; end hour selectable between 8 and 10 PM, with default to 10.
- Prompt for frequency of surveying separated for week- and weekend days: "Please also setup there how often you would like to be surveyed each day! (The more you select, the sooner will you complete the whole test procedure!)"
Possible choices: 2, 3, 4, 5 time(s) a day. With default to 3.
- Prompt for their twitter account: "We would like to follow you on twitter, so we might get explanations for your answers in our questionnaires" – Box with entry possibility
- The app schedules the first notification when to perform the first survey. The app will not tell the participant, when the next survey time will be.

Program follow-up starts:

1. Momentary assessments

- Ask the participant to direct the phone's microphone away from them, be quiet and press "Start Recording"
- The app records the sound environment for 60 seconds, computes 3rd oct band spectrum and LAeq for each second.
for each second: LAeq, Leq, 3rd octave band
for the whole minute: Lmax (maximum of the LAeqs); LA50, LA10, LA90; L50, L10, L90;
Subsequent decision: To send only the 3rd octave band, and to compute anything else ourselves.
The app should show a progress-bar during the recording.
- The app asks the following survey questions: (See Annex 8.2)

8.2. Questionnaires

Question Key in Results files	Answers (x - corresponding number in Results file)
Are you ...? peopleAround	1 - alone 2 - around others (not interacting) 3 - interacting with others
Overall, how would you describe your current environment? pleasant eventful familiar	Sliders: 11 point scales: -5 to 5 unpleasant ----- pleasant uneventful ----- lively unfamiliar ----- familiar Notes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All three adjective pairs ON THE SAME SCREEN. • Sliders should be used – starting position: completely on the left side • ALL sliders MUST be moved, otherwise advance to next window is disabled • “Please move all the sliders even if it is back to the initial position!”
Specifically, how would you describe your SOUND environment of your current location? soundPleasant soundEventful	unpleasant ----- pleasant uneventful ----- lively (sliders, 11 point scales: -5 to 5)

How is the impact of the sound environment on the activity you were engaged in? soundImpact	distracting ----- supportive (slider, 11 point scale: -5 to 5)
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ONLY WHEN OUTSIDE

What are the most prominent features that you can see? viewElements	1 - natural (e.g. mountains, seas, woods, trees, meadows, deserts, parks) 2 - civil engineering structures (e.g. roads, bridges, railway lines) 3- urban city centre (e.g. buildings, bureaus, shopping centres, restaurants, shops) 4 - suburban (e.g. houses, residential areas etc.) 5 - industrial (factories, production facilities, working sites)
What are the main sound sources that you can hear? (multiple choice allowed) outsideSoundSources (outsideSoundSourcesFree)	1 - bird or other animal sounds 2 - wind 3 - water / rain 4 - normal communication (e.g. people talking) 5 - crowds of people 6 - music 7 - sport activities 8 - road traffic 9 - railway 10 - aircraft 11 - mechanical sounds (e.g. construction, industry) 13 (!) - other: _____

ONLY WHEN INSIDE

Can you see the outside environment (e.g. through the window)? outsideVisible If YES: What is the most prominent element? viewElements	1 - Yes 2 - No <i>SAME LIST AS WHEN OUTSIDE</i>
What do you hear from outside? outsideSoundSources	<i>SAME LIST AS WHEN OUTSIDE</i> +: 12 - nothing

<p>What do you hear from inside? insideSoundSource</p>	<p>1 - sounds from inside the room in which I am located (e.g. speech, machines, music/TV, people's activities) 2 - internal sounds from outside the room in which I am located (e.g. speech, machines, music/TV, people's activities) 3 - nothing 4 - other: _____</p>
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QUESTIONS CONTINUED FOR BOTH IN-/OUTSIDE

<p>All in all, at present, what is your current mood? mood</p>	<p>bad ----- good (slider, 11 point scale: -5 to 5)</p>
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2. End-of-week questionnaires – one at each Friday and one at the last Sunday

<p>Overall, what was the impact of the SOUND ENVIRONMENT on your wellbeing over the week? soundImpact</p>	<p>SLIDER: negative ----- positive (11 point scale: -5 to 5)</p>
<p>Over the last week, what was the impact of the LANDSCAPE on your wellbeing? landscapeImpact</p>	<p>SLIDER: negative ----- positive (11 point scale: -5 to 5)</p>
<p>To what extent was the week typical for your life? typical</p>	<p>SLIDER: untypical ----- typical (11 point scales: -5 to 5)</p>

3. Final assessment

<p>Questions on the overall environment of the last 2-3 weeks (<i>see above</i>):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overall, what was the impact of the SOUND ENVIRONMENT on your wellbeing all over the experiment? soundImpact - All over the experiment, what was the impact of the LANDSCAPE on your wellbeing? landscapeImpact - To what extent was the period all over the experiment typical for your life? typical 	
<p>To what extent do you agree to the statement "I am sensitive to noise" noise_sensitivity</p>	<p>1 - not at all 2 - a little 3 - moderately 4 - fairly</p>

<p>Quality of life during the whole study:</p> <p>Personal Wellbeing Index (5th edition) International Wellbeing Group (2013). Personal Wellbeing Index. Melbourne: Australian Centre on Quality of Life, Deakin University (http://www.acqol.com.au/instruments#measures)</p> <p>How satisfied are you with...?</p> <p>1. your standard of living? [Standard of Living] PWI_standard_of_living</p> <p>2. your health? [Personal Health] PWI_health</p> <p>3. what you are achieving in life? [Achieving in Life] PWI_achiev_in_life</p> <p>4. your personal relationships? [Personal Relationships] PWI_relationships</p> <p>5. how safe you feel? [Personal Safety] PWI_safety</p> <p>6. feeling part of your community? [Community-Connectedness] PWI_community_connectedness</p> <p>7. your future security? [Future Security] PWI_future_security</p>	<p>5 - very</p> <p>To be consistent, sliders have been used (11 point scales: 0 to 10)</p> <p>0 ... 10 point (unipolar) scale:</p> <p>0 - No satisfaction at all ... Completely satisfied - 10</p>
<p>WHO-5</p> <p>Over the past (approx.) 2 weeks...</p> <p>... I have felt cheerful and in good spirits WHO_cherful</p> <p>... I have felt calm and relaxed WHO_calm</p> <p>... I have felt active and vigorous WHO_active</p> <p>... I woke up feeling fresh and rested WHO_fresh</p> <p>... my daily life has been filled with things that interest me WHO_interesting_things</p>	<p>Here, as the wording is important, we left the checkbox presentation.</p> <p>5 All of the time 4 Most of the time 3 More than half the time 2 Less than half the time 1 Some of the time 0 At no time</p>

4. Common for all assessments

-
- The app sends the data to our servers [if network not available or server cannot be reached, then the app schedules background data sending at a later time (e.g. in evening)]
 - The app thanks the participant for contribution and schedules the next assessment time.

After the last assessment

- The app states that this was the end of the whole test procedure and thanks the user for participation
- The app proposes to download and use “Noise Capture” app by Ifsttar to contribute to real noisiness mapping of our cities: <http://noise-planet.org/noisecapture.html>
- If you’ve enjoyed participating using this app, there is another app available that will allow you to record your sound experiences all over the world, and it is available at: <https://www.transifex.com/LAE/noisecapture/>

8.3. Calculation of actual aircraft event noise levels during the AnimApp surveys

During the surveys with the AnimApp it might have happened that one or more aircraft were flying nearby the location where the survey was taken. It was considered of interest to have an estimate of the aircraft noise level received at the survey location. For that purpose, the following procedure has been adopted:

For each survey, the OpenSky network database is queried to obtain all available data within $\pm 0.4^\circ$ of the survey Latitude-Longitude and 2 hours previous to the end of the survey. The results of this query are downloaded and filtered again to retain only the flight operations whose closest point of approach (CPA) is less than 7 km and at that moment is within 10 minutes to the end of the survey or during the survey time (in case the survey duration is longer than 10 minutes). Note that several aircraft events may be found in the database at that time. Each of these events will then be handled individually. On the contrary, it may also be possible that during the survey an aircraft passed by, which was not detected by the OpenSky network (e.g. small aircraft without ADS-B transponder on-board). In that case no noise level can be predicted, so that event would get lost.

For each of these operations the aircraft type and flight track are known, so they can be processed by the SONDEO model to estimate L_{Amax}, L_{Aeq} and duration of the event at the survey position. For each of these operation-event the following data is provided:

filename	survey unique identifier e.g. 000187_20210718_215955_surveyResults.json
Country	UK/SLO
ModeS	A unique identifier of the aircraft ADSB transponder
CallSign	Aircraft operation broadcasted by the transponder. It is similar to the airline's flight number.
surveyStartDateLocal	Local date-time of the survey start and noise recording.
surveyFinishDateLocal	Local date-time of the survey end .
tCPA_Local	Time of the aircraft Closest Point of Approach (CPA) to the survey position.
surveyStartDateUTC surveyFinishDateUTC, tCPA_UTC	same as above, but in UTC time
tCPA-tEnd_sec	Number of seconds from the CPA time to the survey finish time. It is a negative number to indicate the CPA occurs before the end of the survey. Minimum is -600 seconds since only 10minutes are filtered.
tCPA-tStart_sec	Number of seconds from the start of survey to CPA time. Positive if CPA occurs after the start of the survey.
isInFirstMin	Y/N. Yes if CPA time occurs in the first minute after the survey start time (during the survey recording)
ICAO	ICAO designator of the aircraft (e.g. A20N
Airbus A320 neo)	

AD	A-Approach/D-Departure
altCPA_m	Altitude in meters of the aircraft CPA.
gspCPA_kts	Ground speed of the aircraft in knots at CPA
distCPA_m	Distance in meters from survey position to aircraft CPA (includes horizontal distance and altitude)
Duration_sec	Estimated time in seconds above L _{Amax} -10dBA at survey position.
L _{Amax}	Estimated maximum noise level at survey position.
L _{Aeq}	Estimated equivalent noise level at survey position.

Comparing the predicted noise levels with those measured with ANOTEC's noise monitoring system, installed at various airports (e.g. for A320 departures), it can be seen that the predicted levels are well in line with the measurements. It can therefore be assumed that the provided levels are a good indication of the actual aircraft noise level that have occurred during the surveys. It is noted that all aircraft noise levels considered here are valid for the outdoor situation only. No attempt has been made to predict indoor noise levels for those events where the survey was taken inside.

For each survey, the different aircraft events found within the 10 minutes before the end of the survey (if any) are combined calculating the equivalent noise level referred to ten minutes, keeping also the maximum LAmax of the events. As a subset of these, the events falling in the first minute of the survey (if any) are also combined. Table “momentary” of the survey results is then enriched with the following columns:

fileName	nEvts10 min	LAeq_10 min	LAmax10 min	nEvts1min	LAeq_1min	LAmax1min
118720_20210611_135733_surveyResults.json	5	33.0	47.2	1	33.5	41.3
000187_20210718_215955_surveyResults.json	1	37.7	52.0	0		
000187_20210604_081137_surveyResults.json						

nEvts10min	number of aircraft events in the 10 minute period before SurveyFinishTime
LAeq_10min	the LAeq related to 10 minutes, combining all the aircraft events detected in the 10 minute interval
LAmax10min	the maximum of the LAmax levels found for all aircraft events in the 10 minute interval
nEvts1min	number of aircraft events in the 1 minute period after SurveyStartTime

LAeq_1min	the LAeq related to 1 minute, combining all the aircraft events detected in the 1 minute interval
LAmx1min	the maximum of the LAmx levels found for all aircraft events in the 1 minute interval

8.4. AnimApp: computed acoustic parameters

INPUT DATA:

- Several 1-minute-long sound recordings transferred into a series of 1/3rd octave band spectrums.
- (in total I pieces.)
- User ID-s for each recording. For each user ID different number of recordings are available (denoted by I)

NOMENCLATURE:

- n : time indexes (length N) of the sequential spectrums of 1 recording
- f_c : centre frequencies (length of F) of the 3rd octave bands (20, 25, ..., 12.5k, 16k Hz)
- $S_{dB}(f_c, n)$: 1/3rd octave band spectrum component in decibels as function of time- and frequency indexes

CALCULATED TEMPORARY DATA:

- The power spectrum is computed from the 1/3rd octave band spectrum (i.e. dB->lin):

$$S(f_c, n) = 10^{S_{dB}(f_c, n)/10}$$

- The average sound environment is computed for each participant (resulting in one reference spectrum and a reference SPL value per userID):
 1. For each 1-minute recording an equivalent spectrum is computed (from the 1.5 sec long slices' spectrums – 65.536 point FFT on 44.100 Hz sampling frequency)

$$S_{eq, dB}(f_c) = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{1}{N'} \sum_{n'} S(f_c, n) \right)$$

In the calculation only those spectrums are considered in the mean, for which the corresponding SPL(n) level is between L10 and L90 in order to omit the outliers from the averaging. (This is denoted by n' and N' , i.e. only selected indexes are used.)

2. From the 1-minute recordings of different hours, the average is computed:

$$S_{avg, dB}(f_c) = \frac{1}{I} \sum_i S_{eq, dB}^i(f_c)$$

This is the average spectrum (please note: NOT the overall equivalent spectrum!), which is considered as the *average sound environment* of the participant. By the lack of calibration of the mobile phones, this spectrum, which is unique for each participant,

is used as one **reference**, labelled **reAvg**. When using this reference, from all measured spectrums (S_{dB}) this spectrum is subtracted.

3. Finally from the average spectrum an average SPL is calculated by summing the spectral coefficients:

$$SPL_{mean} = 10 \log_{10} \sum_{f_c} 10^{S_{avg,dB}(f_c,n)/10}$$

This mean SPL for each user ID was used as a second **reference**, labelled **reSPL**, to shift all the spectral data. This offsetting was applied in order to measure the acoustic quantities normalised to the mean SPL sound environment of the given user.

- To derive acoustical parameters, 3 sets have been computed using different references:

1. **uncal**: the original recordings are used, no calibration is done:

$$\tilde{S}_{dB}(f_c, n) = S_{dB}(f_c, n)$$

2. **reAvg**: the average spectrum is used as reference

$$\tilde{S}_{dB}(f_c, n) = S_{dB}(f_c, n) - S_{avg,dB}(f_c)$$

3. **reSPL**: the mean SPL (i.e. a dB number) is used as reference:

$$\tilde{S}_{dB}(f_c, n) = S_{dB}(f_c, n) - SPL_{mean}$$

In the followings, all computed metrics were calculated by using one of these relative spectral data.

- In most of the cases the power spectrum has to be used, which is:

$$\tilde{S}(f_c, n) = 10^{\tilde{S}_{dB}(f_c, n)/10}$$

- The sound pressure level for one measurement's one spectrum (which is in fact the Leq for the particular 1.5 second recording) is calculated by summation of the spectral bins according to the Parseval theorem:

$$SPL(n) = 10 \log_{10} \sum_{f_c} \tilde{S}(f_c, n)$$

This metric represents the Sound Pressure Level as the function of time over one 60 sec long measurement period.

- Bandlimited SPL, to 100, 200, 4000 Hz are calculated by summing only parts of the spectrum in order to measure low-, middle- and high frequency fluctuation of the Sound Pressure Level:

- $SPL_{100}(n) = 10 \log_{10} \sum_{f_c \leq 100\text{Hz}} \tilde{S}(f_c, n)$
- $SPL_{200}(n) = 10 \log_{10} \sum_{f_c \leq 200\text{Hz}} \tilde{S}(f_c, n)$
- $SPL_{4000}(n) = 10 \log_{10} \sum_{f_c \geq 4000\text{Hz}} \tilde{S}(f_c, n)$
- $SPL_{mid}(n) = 10 \log_{10} \sum_{200\text{Hz} < f_c < 4000\text{Hz}} \tilde{S}(f_c, n)$

- A-weighted sound pressure level is calculated by weighting the spectral data with the standard A-filter coefficients, in order to accommodate the measurements to the characteristics of human hearing.

$$SPLA(n) = 10 \log_{10} \sum_{f_c} \tilde{S}(f_c, n) \cdot F_A(f_c)$$

$F_A(f_c)$: Frequency response of A-weighting filter

FINAL COMPUTED METRICS:

- **Equivalent pressure levels:**

- L_{eq} , LA_{eq} parameters: Equivalent levels are calculated over time as used in acoustics:

$$L_{eq} = 10 \log_{10} \frac{1}{N} \sum_n 10^{SPL(n)/10} \quad LA_{eq} = 10 \log_{10} \frac{1}{N} \sum_n 10^{SPLA(n)/10}$$

This equivalent continuous sound level for one 1-minute recording is the sound level in decibels, having the same total sound energy as the fluctuating level.

- SPL_{std} , $SPLA_{eq_std}$ parameters: Standard deviation of SPL in dB:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacksquare \quad SPL_{std} &= \sqrt{\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_n (SPL(n) - \frac{1}{N} \sum_n SPL(n))^2} \\ \blacksquare \quad SPLA_{std} &= \sqrt{\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_n (SPLA(n) - \frac{1}{N} \sum_n SPLA(n))^2} \end{aligned}$$

These quantities represent the amount of fluctuation around the mean SPL. This gives information about steadiness vs. fluctuating-behaviour of the measurement.

- L_n , LA_n , $n = 10, 50, 90$ (L_{10}, L_{50}, L_{90}) parameters: The acoustic percentiles are calculated, representing the SPL (and SPLA) level, which was exceeded in n percentage of the measurement time.

- L_{dyn} , LA_{dyn} parameters: Dynamic range of the SPL fluctuation:

$$L_{dyn} = L_{10} - L_{90} \quad LA_{dyn} = LA_{10} - LA_{90}$$

- $L_{eq_LP_100Hz}$: very-low frequency content: same as L_{eq} , calculated with $SPL_{100}(n)$
- $L_{eq_LP_100Hz_std}$: same as L_{eq_std} , calculated with $SPL_{100}(n)$
- $L_{eq_LP_200Hz}$: low-frequency content: same as L_{eq} , calculated with $SPL_{200}(n)$
- $L_{eq_LP_200Hz_std}$: same as L_{eq_std} , calculated with $SPL_{200}(n)$
- $L_{eq_HP_4kHz}$: high-frequency content: same as L_{eq} , calculated with $SPL_{4000}(n)$
- $L_{eq_HP_4kHz_std}$: same as L_{eq_std} , calculated with $SPL_{4000}(n)$
- L_{eq_mid} : mid-frequency content: same as L_{eq} , calculated with $SPL_{mid}(n)$
- $L_{eq_mid_std}$: same as L_{eq_std} , calculated with $SPL_{mid}(n)$

FOR THESE PARAMETERS, THE ORIGINAL, UNCALIBRATED SPECTRUM IS USED:

• **The spectral centroid:**

- *Spectral_centroid* parameter: Center of mass (center of gravity) of the spectral data: (calculated for the original input spectrum). The SC parameter is intended to reveal low frequency / high frequency ratio by the definition:

$$SC(n) = \frac{\sum_{f_c} f_c S(f_c, n)}{\sum_{f_c} S(f_c, n)}$$

Traditionally the spectral centroid is used to measure the perceptual brightness of the sound (manifesting in higher SC parameter). In the present application the SC parameter may be used to differentiate between low frequency noise originating potentially from airborne noise and other high frequency background noises.

- *Spectral_centroid_mean*: temporal mean of spectral centroids in a single measurement (in 60sec)

$$SC = \frac{1}{N} \sum_n SC(n)$$

- *Spectral_centroid_std*: standard deviation of spectral centroids

$$SC_{std} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_n (SC(n) - SC)^2}$$

• **The spectral flatness:**

- *Spectral_flatness* parameter: The SF parameter quantifies the tonality of the measured signal. By definition it is calculated as the ratio of geometric and arithmetic mean of the spectra:

$$SF(n) = \frac{\sqrt[F]{\prod_{f_c} S(f_c, n)}}{\sum_{f_c} S(f_c, n)}$$

By definition the SF parameter is

- 0 for harmonic signals
- 1 for pink noise = totally flat 3rd oct band spectrum

The parameter is intended to reveal the presence of tonal components

- *Spectral_flatness_mean*: temporal mean of spectral flatness:

$$SF = \frac{1}{N} \sum_n SF(n)$$

- Spectral_flatness_std: standard deviation of spectral flatnesses:

$$SF_{std} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_n (SF(n) - SF)^2}$$

8.5. Repeated correlation plots

This Illustration depicts correlation plots for selected bivariate associations. In the plots, dots reflect the bivariate responses of all measurements, and lines are fitted to the data from each participant and indicate the linear relationship between the respective two variables for each participant.

8.6. A summary of the mixed model analysis

Fixed coefficients	Null Model	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6
Intercept	2.51 (0.41;6.16)***	0.34 (0.88;0.39)	-2.04 (1.95;-1.05)	-0.41 (1.31;-0.31)	0.72 (0.78;0.92)	0.25 (0.84 ;0.30)	0.28 (0.89;0.56)
Sensitivity to noise							
Mood mean		0.75 (0.28;2.68)*					0.55 (0.38;1.44)
PWI_sum			0.09 (0.04;2.38)*				
WHO_sum				0.19 (0.08 ;2.32)*			
soundPleas Median					0.63 (0.25;2.5)*		0.23 (0.36;0.64)
soundPleas Mean						0.90 (0.31;2.89)**	
Pseudo R² Statistics							
R ² _{Global}	0.52	0.59	0.61	0.58	0.21	0.26	0.47
R ² _{Pseudo Fixe-effect}	0	0.27	0.23	0.21	0.21	0.26	0.26
Random parameters							
Participants	1.73 (1.32)	1.10 (1.05)	1.37 (1.95)	1.32 (1.15)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0.72 (0.85)
Residual	1.61 (1.27)	1.44 (1.20)	1.41 (1.19)	1.47 (1.21)	2.52 (1.59)	2.37 (1.54)	1.83 (1.35)
Goodness of fit							
AIC	103.9	100.2	108.9	107.2	101.5	99.5	102.1

0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Fixed coefficients	Model 7	Model 8	Model 9
Intercept	0.78 (0.52;1.51)	0.61 (0.63;0.97)	1.58 (0.58;22.71)*
SoundImpact median	0.75 (0.19;3.92)***		
SoundImpact mean		0.88 (0.26;3.42)**	
Leq_mid_reAvg last			0.06 (0.03 ;2.08).
Pseudo R² Statistics			
R ² _{Global}	0.39	0.33	0.64
R ² _{Pseudo Fixe-effect}	0.39	0.33	0.14
Random parameters			
Participants	0.00 (0.00)	0.00 (0.00)	1.82 (1.35)
Residual	1.94 (1.39)	2.14 (1.46)	1.34 (1.16)
Goodness of fit			
AIC	95.7	97.47	100.6

0 `****' 0.001 `***' 0.01 `*' 0.05 `.' 0.1 ` ' 1

